

Quaternary vertebrate fauna of Bulgaria – composition, chronology and impoverishment

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Abstract. This study presents for the first time summarized data on 759 species/taxa (628 species at least) of six classes of Quaternary vertebrates of Bulgaria: Chondrichthyes (1); Actinopterygii (34); Amphibia (18); Reptilia (33); Aves (299); and Mammalia (374). The richest fauna has been recorded in the Late Pleistocene (285 species), followed by the Calabrian (255). Bulgaria has lost 32.3% of its former total Quaternary vertebrate fauna. The number of the lost taxa is as follows: species (245), genera (80), families (16), orders (5), of them three mammalian (Perissodactyla, Proboscidea, and Primates), and two avian (Otidiformes and Pteroclidiformes). Extinct families are: one amphibian (Palaeobatrachidae); two reptilian (Varanidae and Elapidae); three avian (Gruidae, Otididae, and Pteroclididae), and ten mammalian (Dipodidae, Eomyidae, Hystricidae, Ochotonidae, Hyaenidae, Phocidae, Equidae, Rhinocerotidae, Elephantidae, and Cercopithecidae). After the small mammals (mainly Cricetidae; 52 taxa), the composition of bovids (27 taxa) and canids (13 taxa) impoverished in a higher extent. The biggest number of recorded vertebrate families is found in the Meghalayan (79), followed by the Greenlandian (63) and the Late Pleistocene (62). At order and family levels, the most varied was the vertebrate fauna in the Meghalayan (39 orders, 79 families). In the Calabrian, the number of genera was a three times greater than in the Northgrippian, which indicates more diversified paleoenvironment. One genus, 25 species, and one subspecies have been described as new to the science from the Quaternary localities in Bulgaria.

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INTRODUCTION

In the last decades, a number of studies have been conducted on the past distribution of some recent large mammals and birds on the territory of Bulgaria. Most of them deal with the large terrestrial mammals (*e.g.*, Spassov, 1997a, b, 2003; Boev, 2017a, 2018a, 2019a, b, 2020a, b, 2021a, b, 2022a, b, d, in press), although some summarizing data on birds (Boev, 1988, 1997a, 1999a, 2003, 2019c, 2020c), reptiles (Boev, 2017b) and amphibians (Boev,

2021c) have also been published. The comprehensive study of Popov (2018) outlined in detail the Quaternary micromammalian (Eulypotyphla, Chiroptera, Lagomorpha, Rodentia) fauna of Bulgaria. As studies in this field were accelerated in this period, the abundant new records significantly contributed to the overall knowledge on the faunal diversity and species distribution and, in some cases, their extinctions in the country. The present study is the first attempt to summarize the abundant and scattered information on Quaternary vertebrates in

Bulgaria. The hidden data for zoologists have been extracted from the numerous archeological or interdisciplinary studies, often published in less-accessible or local editions. This makes the present study a pioneer work on the overall view and estimation of the Bulgarian Quaternary vertebrate fauna.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The present study gathers all available literature data on the records of bone/teeth remains of fishes, amphibians, reptiles, birds, and mammals that are scattered across multiple and diverse sources, including local regional publications, museums, and collections, as well as some unpublished data. A complete bibliography of Bulgarian archeozoological literature (on vertebrates) is provided in the reference section. A total of 759 species/forms of Vertebrata J-B. Lamarck, 1801, including 245 fossil taxa, were collected (see the [Appendix](#)). This study covers all species/taxa recorded in Bulgaria through bone and teeth fossil/subfossil remains. Some taxa are listed with their current taxonomic status, along with the names they were published with. The chronostratigraphy follows Cohen *et al.* (2013): Gelasian (GE) 2.588–1.800 Ma (covering parts of the former Late Pliocene–Early Pleistocene); Calabrian (CA) 1.800–0.774 Ma (Early Pleistocene); Chibanian (CH) 0.770–0.129 Ma (Middle Pleistocene); Late Pleistocene (UP) 0.129–0.0117 Ma; Greenlandian (GR) 0.0117–0.0082 Ma (Early Holocene); Northgrippian (NO) 0.0082–0.0042 Ma (Middle Holocene); and Meghalayan (ME) 0.0042–0.0001 Ma (Late Holocene). Most of the figures illustrating extinct Quaternary birds and mammals represent previously unpublished original drawings by Bulgarian wildlife artists (Figs 1–7).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This paper provides a synthesized review of the Bulgarian archeozoology and Quaternary paleozoology (except for a few publications on archeological remains of invertebrates, shell molluscs). Numerous studies on the animal bone remains of Quaternary deposits (both of anthropogenic and natural accumulation) have been done by British, Bulgarian, Czech, French, German, Dutch, Hungarian, Japanese, North Macedonian, Polish, Slovak, Spanish, and Turkish zoologists, archeologists, paleontologists or local historians. One hundred and thirty-seven records have been incompletely identified up to genus level (sp. indet.). Two records have

been identified up to family level (gen. indet.), and eight records to subfamily level (gen. indet.). Identifications such as “cf.” and “ex gr.” were combined with the relevant taxa, which were firmly identified (when listed). In total, the Quaternary record of vertebrates in Bulgaria covers at least 628 species ([Appendix A](#)).

Impoverishment of the Quaternary vertebrate fauna of Bulgaria

Presented data show that ~1/3 of the Bulgarian Quaternary fauna of vertebrates has been lost in the last ~2.58 Ma. At least 245 taxa (species and genera) were lost from the modern territory of the country. They include both globally extinct (fossil) and disappeared (recent taxa whose current ranges do not include the territory of the country) vertebrates in the Quaternary of Bulgaria. As for birds, this group includes nine species (*Pelecanus onocrotalus*, *Aegyptius monachus*, *Phasianus colchicus*, *Grus grus*, *Otis tarda*, *Pterocles alchata*, *Tetrax tetrax*, *Falco cherrug*, and *Pyrrhocorax pyrrhocorax*), which do not breed in the country. Separate very rare cases of successful nesting/breeding in the last decades have been recorded for *P. onocrotalus* and *F. cherrug*, while *A. monachus* is subject of a reintroduction program and first successful breeding occurred in 2022. *Phasianus colchicus* is an extinct species (the native *P. colchicus colchicus* subspecies) and all present pheasants (common pheasants) originated from the farmed hybrid birds (*P. c. torquatus* x *P. c. mongolicus*). *Lagopus muta* has only one single record in Bulgaria (Miltschew and Georgiewa, 1998). *Pterocles alchata* breeds in Southwest Europe and neighboring Turkey, and it is very likely that the species has nested in the past in the open steppe regions of Northern Bulgaria and the Upper Thracian Plain. At present, this species is a rare vagrant in the country. The only record of *P. pyrrhocorax* in Bulgaria is from Schranke and Wolf (1938) and the species has been considered extinct in the country.

The complete list below (see also the [Appendix](#)) includes both (1) the largest representatives of the widely spread Pleistocene megafauna in the Holarctic Region, and (2) many of the smallest terrestrial (land) mammals (micromammals, shrews, rodents, bats):

- Actinopterygii – *Thunnus thynnus*;
- Amphibia (Palaeobatrachidae) – *Eopelobates*;
- Reptilia – *Mabuya*, Varanidae gen. indet., Elapidae gen. indet.;
- Aves (Non-Passeriformes): *Pelecanus onocrotalus*, *Geronticus balcanicus*, *Aegyptius monachus*, *Circus haemusensis*, *Gypaetus barbatus*, *Gyps*

Fig. 1. a) *Aquila kurochkini* Boev, 2013. Eagle of Evgeniy Kurochkin; b) *Circaetus haemusensis* Boev, 2015. Haemus Snake-eagle; c) *Gyps bochenskii* Boev, 2010. Gryffon of Zygmunt Bocheński; d) *Falco bakalovi* Boev, 1999. Falcon of Petar Bakalov (Drawings: Zlatozar Z. Boev).

bochenskii, *Falco bakalovi*, *F. cherrug*, *Chauvireria balcanica*, *Ch. bulgarica*, *Lagopus balcanicus*, *L. lagopus*, *L. muta*, *Lyrurus tetrrix*, *Perdix palaeoperdix*, *Phasianus colchicus*, *Tetrao partium*, *Fulica atra pontica*, *Gallinula balcanica*, *Porzana*

botunensis, *Grus grus*, *Otis khosatzkii*, *O. tarda*, *Tetrax tetrax*, *Actitis balcanica*, *Bubo scandiacus*, *Strix nebulosa*, and *Apus baranensis*;

• Aves (Passeriformes): *Corvus praecorax*, *Pyrhocorax pyrrhocorax*, *Coccothraustes balcanicus*,

C. simeonovi, *Loxia patevi*, *Alauda xerarvensis*, *Eremophila prealpestris*, *Galerida bulgarica*, *Lullula balcanica*, *Melanocorypha donchevi*, and *Regulus bulgaricus*;

• Mammalia (Micromammalia): *Asoriculus gibberodon*, *Beremendia fissidens*, *Crocidura zorzii*, *Mafia csarnotensis*, *Petenya hungarica*, *Sorex minutissimus*, *S. runtonensis*, *S. subaraneus*, *Erina-*

Fig. 2. a) *Chauvireria balcanica* Boev, 1997. Balkan Partridge of Cécile Mourer-Chauviré (Drawing: Viktor Vasilev); b) *Lagopus balcanicus* Boev, 1995. Balkan ptarmigan (Drawing: Viktor Vasilev); c) *Tetrao partium* (Kretzoi, 1962). Partial black grouse (Drawing: Viktor Vasilev); d) *Gallinula balcanica* Boev, 1999. Balkan moorhen (Drawing: Assen Ignatov); e) *Porzana botunensis* Boev, 2015. Botunya River crake (Drawing: Assen Ignatov); f) *Otis* aff. *khosatzkii* Bochenski, Kurochkin, 1987. Khosatzki's Bustard (Drawing: Viktor Vasilev).

ceus lechei, *Desmana polonica*, *Desmana* sp. indet., *Quyania polonica*, *Scalopoides copernici*, *Talpa csarnotana*, *T. levantis*, *Hypolagus brachygnathus*, *Trischizolagus* sp. indet., *Ochotona transcaucasica*, *O. polonica*, *O. pusilla*, *Rhinolophus lissiensis*, *R.*

macrorhinus, *Barbastella darjeligensis*, *Myotis gundersheimensis*, *M. schaubi*, *M. estramonensis*, *Plecotus crassidens*, *Hystrix refossa*, *Hystrix* sp. indet., *Allocricetus bursae*, *A. ehiki*, *Allophaiomys pliocaenicus*, *Allophaiomys* sp. indet., *Arvicola*

Fig. 3. a) *Actitis balcanica* Boev, 1998. Balkan sandpiper (Drawing: Zlatozar Z. Boev); b) *Apus baranensis* Janossy 1977. Beremend swift (Drawing: Zlatozar Z. Boev); c) *Pica praepica* Boev, 2021. European pre-magpie (Drawing: Viktor Vasilev); d) *Coccothraustes simeonovi* Boev, 1998. Hawfinch of Simeon Simeonov (Drawing: Assen Ignatov); e) *Loxia patevi* Boev, 1999. Crossbill of Pavel Patev (Drawing: Assen Ignatov); f) *Alauda xerarvensis* Boev, 2012. Dry-field skylark (Drawing: Georgi Pchelarov).

cantianus, *A. chozaricus*, *A. kalmakensis*, *Bjornkurtentia canterranensis*, *Borsodia altisinuosa*, *B. arankoides*, *B. fejervaryi*, *B. hungarica*, *B. petenyii*, *Castillomys* sp. indet., *Clethrionomys primitivus*, *Clethrionomys* sp. indet., *Cricetus nanus*,

C. runtonensis, *Cseria opsia*, *Eolagurus gromovi*, *E. luteus*, *Jordanomys major*, *Kolymnomys major*, *Lagurodon arankae*, *L. praepannonicus*, *Lagurus lagurus*, *L. pannonicus*, *L. transiens*, *L. transylvanicus*, *Microtus arvalidens*, *M. arvalinus*, *M. burgon-*

Fig. 4. a) *Eremophila prealpestris* Boev, 2012. Pre-Alpine horned lark; b) *Galerida bulgarica* Boev, 2012. Bulgarian crested lark; c) *Lullula balcanica* Boev, 2012. Balkan woodlark; d) *Melanocorypha donchevi* Boev, 2012. Lark of Stefan Donchev (Drawings: Georgi Pchelarov).

diae, *M. deucalion*, *Microtus gregaloides/gregalis*, *M. hintoni*, *M. levis*, *M. nivalinus*, *M. nivaloides*, *M. oconomus*, *M. pliocaenicus*, *M. savini*/*M. pusillus*, *Mimomys reidi*, *M. blanci*, *M. pitymyoides*, *M. pliocaenicus*, *M. pusillus*, *M. reidi*, *M. savini*, *M. stenokory*, *M. tornensis*, *Myodes kretzoi*, *Myomys pitymyoides*, *M. pusillus*, *Pliomys chalinei*, *P. coronensis*, *P. episcopalis*, *P. lenki*, *P. simplicior*, *Prolagurus* sp. indet., *Ungaromys nanus*, *Vilanya exilis*, *V. petenyii*, *Allactaga major*, *Apodemus uralensis*, *Dinaromys dalmatinus*, *Micromys praeminutus*, *Micromys* sp. indet., *Rhagapodemus frequens*, *Sylvaemus dominans*, *Eliomys* sp. indet., *Glis sackdillingensis*, *G. minor*, *Reteliomys podumcensis*, *Estramomys simplex*, *Nannospalax odessanus*, *Pliospalax compositodontus*, *Marmota bobak*, *Spermophilus nogaici*, *S. primigenius*, and *Tamias* sp. indet.;

• Mammalia (Macromammalia): *Canis etruscus*, *C. mosbachensis*, *Cuon alpinus europaeus*,

C. stehlini, *Nyctereutes tingi*, *N. megamastoides*, *Vulpes alopecoides*, *V. praeglacialis*, *V. lagopus*, *Ursus thibetanus*, *U. wenzensis*, *U. deningeri*, *U. etruscus*, *U. ingressus*, *U. minimus*, *U. rossicus*, *U. savini*, *U. spelaeus*, *Baranogale balcanica*, *Cynaonyx antiqua*, *Martes vetus*, *M. wenzensis*, *Meles thorali*, *Pannonictis ardea*, *Vormela petenyii*, *Chasmaporthetes lunensis*, *Crocota crocuta spelaea*, *Pliocrocota perrieri*, *Acinonyx pardinensis*, *Felis lunensis*, *F. minuta*, *Homotherium crenatidens*, *H. latidens*, *Lynx issiodorensis*, *L. spelaeus*, *Megantereon cultridens*, *Panthera fossilis*, *P. gombaszogensis*, *P. leo europaea*, *P. leo fossilis*, *P. pardus*, *P. spelaea*, *Puma pardoides*, *Monachus monachus*, *Alces alces*, *Cervalces latifrons*, *Cervus philisi*, *Eucloceros ctenoides*, *E. senezensis*, *Megaloceros giganteus*, *Megaloceros* sp. indet., *Rangifer tarandus*, *Sus strozzi*, *Bison bonasus*, *B. priscus*, *Bos brachycerous*, *B. primigenius*, *Capra caucasica*, *C. ibex*, *Gallogoral* sp. indet., *Gazellospira torti-*

Fig. 5. a) *Regulus bulgaricus* Boev, 1999. Bulgarian kinglet; b) *Cuon alpinus europaeus* Bourguignat, 1868. European Dhole (Drawing: Zlatozar Z. Boev); c) *Pliocrocota perrieri* (Croizet, Jobert, 1828). Perrier's Pliocene Hyaena (Drawing: Velizar Simeonovski); d) *Acinonyx pardinensis* Croizet, Jobert, 1828. Giant Cheetah (Drawing: Velizar Simeonovski).

cornis, *Gazellospira* sp. indet., *Hemitragus bonali*, *H. cedrensis*, *H. orientalis*, *Leptobos* sp. indet., *Megalovis balcanicus*, *M. latifrons*, *Ovis antiqua*, *Pliotragus* sp. indet., *Procamptoceras brivatense*, *Procamptoceras* sp. indet., *Saiga tatarica*, *Soergelia intermedia*, *Soergelia* sp. indet., *Stephanorhinus etruscus*, *S. kirchbergensis*, *Coelodonta antiquitatis*, *Equus altidens*, *E. caballus germanicus*, *E. mosbachensis*, *E. suessenbornensis*, *E. ferus ferus*, *E. germanicus transylvanicus*, *E. hydruntinus*, *E. latipes*, *E. stehlini*, *E. stenonis*, *Mammuthus trogontherii*, *M. primigenius*, and *Macaca sylvanus*.

Based on the list above, it becomes evident that 16 families of vertebrates have disappeared: one family of amphibians (Palaeobatrachidae); two families of reptiles (Varanidae and Elapidae); three families of birds (Gruidae, Otididae, and Pteroclididae); and ten families of mammals (Dipodidae, Eomyidae, Hystricidae, Ochotonidae, Hyaenidae, Phocidae, Equidae, Rhinocerotidae, Elephantidae, and Cercopithecidae). At present, most of the disap-

peared families (Varanidae, Elapidae, Hystricidae, Hyaenidae, Phocidae, Equidae, Rhinocerotidae, Elephantidae, and Cercopithecidae) have retreated their current ranges southward of Bulgaria and the Balkan Peninsula and even beyond the borders of the European continent. Two families (Dipodidae and Ochotonidae) restricted their ranges northward, and two families (Palaeobatrachidae and Eomyidae) have gone extinct, as they include only fossil representatives.

It is worthy to look at the disappeared vertebrates at genus level. Data show that 80 genera have been lost for the recent vertebrate fauna of Bulgaria: Amphibia (one genus – *Eopelobates*); Reptilia (two genera – *Mabuya* and *Heremites*); Aves (eight genera – *Geronticus*, *Chauvireria*, *Lagopus*, *Lyrurus*, *Grus*, *Otis*, *Tetrax*, *Pterocles*); Mammalia (69 genera – *Asoriculus*, *Beremendia*, *Mafia*, *Petenya*, *Desmana*, *Quyania*, *Scalopoides*, *Hypolagus*, *Trischizolagus*, *Ochotona*, *Hystrix*, *Allocricetus*, *Allophaiomys*, *Allophaiomys*, *Bjornkurtenia*, *Borso-*

Fig. 6. a) *Lynx issiodorensis issiodorensis* (Croizet, Jobert, 1828). Issoire Lynx; b) *Megantereon cultridens* (Cuvier, 1824). Knife-toothed Megantereon; c) *Puma pardoides* Owen, 1846. Eurasian Puma; d) *Eucladoceros senezensis* (Deperet, 1910). Senèze Eucladoceros Deer (Drawings: Velizar Simeonovski).

Fig. 7. a) *Bos primigenius* Bojanus, 1827. Aurochs; b) *Gazellospira torticornis* (Aymard, 1854). Spiral-Horned Antelope; c) *Stephanorhinus etruscus* (Falconer, 1868). Etruscan Rhinoceros; d) *Equus stenonis* Cocchi, 1867. Stenon Zebra (Drawings: Velizar Simeonovski).

dia, *Castillomys*, *Cseria*, *Eolagurus*, *Jordanomys*, *Kolymnomys*, *Lagurodon*, *Lagurus*, *Mimomys*, *Myodes*, *Myomys*, *Pliomys*, *Prolagurus*, *Ungaromys*, *Villanyia*, *Allactaga*, *Dinaromys*, *Rhagapodemus*, *Reteliomys*, *Estramomys*, *Pliospalax*, *Marmota*, *Nyctereutes*, *Baranogale*, *Cyrnaonyx*, *Pannonictis*, *Chasmaporthetes*, *Crocota*, *Pliocrocota*, *Acinonyx*, *Homotherium*, *Lynx*, *Megantereon*, *Panthera*, *Puma*, *Cervalces*, *Eucladoceros*, *Megaloceros*, *Bison*, *Bos*, *Gallogoral*, *Gazellospira*, *Hemitragus*, *Leptobos*, *Megalovis*, *Ovis*, *Pliotragus*, *Procampoceras*, *Soergelia*, *Stephanorhinus*, *Coelodonta*, *Equus*, *Mammuthus*, and *Macaca*).

Environmental events in the Quaternary have clearly impacted mammals (especially small mammals; 28 genera). Carnivores and bovids suffered significant impoverishment as well.

Nyctereutes is an exotic genus for the modern Bulgarian fauna, but *N. procyonoides* (Gray, 1834) invaded the country from the European regions of its introductions. *Lynx* disappeared since the 1940s,

but in the 2000s, *L. lynx* has been recorded in the country again. *Bison* survived until the 17th century (Boev, 2022 b), but in the 1970s *B. bison* was reintroduced (in game farms-reserves). *Ovis* was reintroduced in 1965, when several pairs of *O. gmelini* Blyth, 1841 were released and established the population of the reintroduced mouflons. Although 11 species of *Equus* were registered in the fossil record of Bulgaria, at present only domestic horse and domestic donkey are known in the country.

Fossil (extinct) and disappeared recent taxa

Almost one-third (245; 32.3%) of the recorded taxa in the Quaternary deposits of Bulgaria have gone extinct during the last 2.588 Ma. The bulk of this extinct fauna consists of mammals 179 (214 taxa) and birds (34 taxa). In comparison with the fossil Quaternary mammalian fauna, the recent fauna of mammals, containing 97 species and semispecies (Peshev *et al.*, 2004), and one recently recovered (*Castor fiber*;

Kodzhabashev *et al.*, 2021), is twice poorer. It barely reaches 54.2% of the Quaternary one.

The great majority of fossil mammals in the Bulgarian Quaternary belongs to rodents (62 species), followed by carnivorans (42), and artiodactyls (20) (see Appendix A). In addition, in the Quaternary of Bulgaria, three orders (Perissodactyla, Primates and Proboscidea) have been lost.

The representation of birds is quite different. The fossil bird taxa (26 species and one subspecies), represent 6.4% of the country's modern avifauna (421 species; Ivanov *et al.*, 2020). This means that 26 species and one subspecies are extinct.

The recorded taxa could be separated into two major groups: 1) warm-loving (subtropical/savannah inhabitants), and 2) cold-loving (boreal/steppe elements). Among the first group, there could be listed: amphibians – *Pelobates syriacus*, *Rana dalmatina*; reptiles – *Heremites auratus*, *Mabuya* sp., *Pseudopus apodus*, Varanidae gen. indet., *Elaphe quatuorlineata*, *Eryx* sp., *Elapidae* gen. indet., *Testudo graeca*, and *T. hermanni*; birds – *Pelecanus onocrotalus*, *P. crispus*, *Geronticus balcanicus*, *Tadorna ferruginea*, *T. tadorna*, *Gypaetus barbatus*, *Aegyptius monachus*, *Gyps fulvus*, *G. bochenkii*, *Circaetus gallicus*, *C. haemusensis*, *Hieraaetus fasciatus*, *Chauvireria balcanica*, *C. bulgarica*, *Glareola nordmanni*, *Burrhinus oedicnemus*, *Apus baranensis*, *A. apus*, *Tachymarptis melba*, *Alcedo atthis*, *Merops apiaster*, *Upupa epops*, *Coracias garrulus*, *Petronia petronia*, *Ptyonoprogne rupestris*, *Hirundo daurica*, and *Oriolus oriolus*; mammals – *Crociodura suaveolens*, *Miniopterus schreibersii*, *Hystrix refossa*, *Jordanomys major*, *Microtus pliocaenicus*, *Clethrionomys primitivus*, *Canis aureus*, *Vormela petenyii*, *Pliocrocuta perrieri*, *Panthera leo europaea*, *Homotherium crenatidens*, *H. latidens*, *Acinonyx pardinensis*, *Megantereon cultridens*, *Dama dama*, *Eucladoceros senzensis*, *E. ctenoides*, and *Macaca sylvanus*.

The second group includes: birds – *Bubo scandiacus*, *Strix nebulosa*, *Buteo lagopus*, *Tetrao parvum*, *Lagopus balcanicus*, *Perdix palaeoperdix*, *Melanocorypha donchevi*, *Eremophila prealpestris*, *Numenius phaeopus*, *Tetrax tetrax*, *Otis tarda*, and *O. khosatzkii*; mammals – *Chionomys nivalis*, *Ochotona transcaucasica*, *O. polonica*, *Lepus timidus*, *Lagurus transiens*, *L. transylvanicus*, *L. pannonicus*, *Lagurodon arankae*, *L. praepannonicus*, *Eolagurus gromovi*, *E. luteus*, *Allocricetus bursae*, *A. ehiki*, *Cricetus nanus*, *Pliospalax compositodontus*, *Nannospalax odessanus*, *Spermophilus nogaici*, *S. primigenius*, *Sicista loriger*, *Cuon stehlini*, *C. alpinus*, *Vulpes alopecoides*, *V. lagopus*, *V. praegla-*

cialis, *Ursus spelaeus*, *U. deningeri*, *U. ingressus*, *U. savini*, *U. rossicus*, *Vormela petenyii*, *Megaloceros giganteus*, *Cervalces latifrons*, *Bison priscus*, *Saiga tatarica*, *Megalovis latifrons*, *M. balcanicus*, *Coelodonta antiquitatis*, *Equus mosbachensis*, *E. stenonis*, *E. suessenbornensis*, *E. germanicus*, *E. stehlini*, *E. altidens*, *E. hydruntinus*, *E. ferus*, *E. latipes*, *Mammuthus primigenius*, and others.

The taxa listed above represent only a part of the great variety of the Quaternary vertebrate fauna of Bulgaria.

Chronostratigraphic distribution of vertebrate families

Complete lists of the recorded families of vertebrates in the seven periods of the Quaternary (Cothen, 2013) are presented below:

- Gelasian – 59 families: five amphibian (Salamandridae, Palaeobatrachidae, Bufonidae, Pelobatidae, and Ranidae); ten reptilian (Scincidae, Anguillidae, Lacertidae, Varanidae, Colubridae, Viperidae, Boidae, Elapidae, Testudinidae, and Emydidae); 21 avian (Anatidae, Accipitridae, Phasianidae, Rallidae, Otidae, Scolopacidae, Columbidae, Strigidae, Apodidae, Corvidae, Sturnidae, Fringillidae, Alaudidae, Motacillidae, Paridae, Sittidae, Regulidae, Muscicapidae, Sylviidae, Turdidae, and Emberizidae); and 22 mammalian (Soricidae, Erinaceidae, Talpidae, Leporidae, Ochotonidae, Rhinolophidae, Vespertilionidae, Hystricidae, Cricetidae, Muridae, Gliridae, Eomyidae, Spalacidae, Sciuridae, Canidae, Ursidae, Mustelidae, Hyaenidae, Felidae, Cervidae, Bovidae, Rhinocerotidae, and Equidae).

- A total of 50 families of vertebrates have been recorded in the Calabrian: two reptilian (Varanidae, and Testudinidae); 20 avian (Threskiornithidae, Ardeidae, Accipitridae, Falconidae, Phasianidae, Columbidae, Cuculidae, Strigidae, Apodidae, Picidae, Corvidae, Sturnidae, Fringillidae, Alaudidae, Motacillidae, Laniidae, Muscicapidae, Sylviidae, Turdidae, and Emberizidae); and 28 mammalian (Soricidae, Erinaceidae, Talpidae, Leporidae, Ochotonidae, Rhinolophidae, Vespertilionidae, Hystricidae, Castoridae, Cricetidae, Dipodidae, Sminthidae, Muridae, Gliridae, Spalacidae, Sciuridae, Canidae, Ursidae, Mustelidae, Hyaenidae, Felidae, Cervidae, Suidae, Bovidae, Rhinocerotidae, Equidae, Elephantidae, and Cercopithecidae);

- Chibanian – 40 families: two amphibian (Bufonidae and Pelobatidae); three reptilian (Lacertidae, Colubridae, Testudinidae); ten avian (Accipitridae, Falconidae, Phasianidae, Picidae, Corvidae, Fringillidae, Alaudidae, Hirundinidae, Cinclidae, and

Turdidae); and 25 mammalian (Soricidae, Erinaceidae, Talpidae, Leporidae, Ochotonidae, Vespertilionidae, Hystricidae, Castoridae, Cricetidae, Dipodidae, Sminthidae, Muridae, Gliridae, Spalacidae, Sciuridae, Canidae, Ursidae, Mustelidae, Hyaenidae, Felidae, Cervidae, Bovidae, Rhinocerotidae, Equidae, and Elephantidae);

- Late Pleistocene – 62 families: four reptilian (Lacertidae, Colubridae, Viperidae, and Testudinidae); 30 avian (Accipitridae, Falconidae, Phasianidae, Rallidae, Haematopodidae, Recurvirostridae, Charadriidae, Glareolidae, Scolopacidae, Burhinidae, Laridae, Columbidae, Strigidae, Apodidae, Picidae, Corvidae, Sturnidae, Passeridae, Fringillidae, Alaudidae, Hirundinidae, Motacillidae, Bombycillidae, Prunellidae, Paridae, Sittidae, Muscicapidae, Sylviidae, Turdidae, and Emberizidae); and 29 mammalian (Soricidae, Erinaceidae, Talpidae, Leporidae, Ochotonidae, Rhinolophidae, Vespertilionidae, Hystricidae, Castoridae, Cricetidae, Dipodidae, Sminthidae, Muridae, Gliridae, Spalacidae, Sciuridae, Canidae, Ursidae, Mustelidae, Hyaenidae, Felidae, Phocidae, Suidae, Bovidae, Rhinocerotidae, Equidae, and Elephantidae);

- Greenlandian – 63 families: one actynopterygian (Cyprinidae); two amphibian (Pelobatidae and Ranidae); one reptilian (Testudinidae); 36 avian (Podicipedidae, Pelecanidae, Ardeidae, Phalacrocoracidae, Anatidae, Ciconiidae, Accipitridae, Falconidae, Phasianidae, Rallidae, Gruidae, Otidae, Charadriidae, Scolopacidae, Laridae, Pteroclididae, Columbidae, Strigidae, Apodidae, Alcedinidae, Coraciidae, Picidae, Corvidae, Sturnidae, Passeridae, Fringillidae, Alaudidae, Hirundinidae, Motacillidae, Cinclidae, Paridae, Sittidae, Laniidae, Muscicapidae, Sylviidae, and Turdidae); and 23 mammalian (Soricidae, Talpidae, Leporidae, Ochotonidae, Rhinolophidae, Vespertilionidae, Castoridae, Cricetidae, Dipodidae, Sminthidae, Muridae, Gliridae, Spalacidae, Sciuridae, Canidae, Ursidae, Mustelidae, Felidae, Phocidae, Cervidae, Suidae, Bovidae, and Equidae);

- Northgrippian – 54 families: three actynopterygian (Siluridae, Scombridae, and Cyprinidae); 2 reptilian (Testudinidae and Emydidae); 29 avian (Gaviidae, Podicipedidae, Pelecanidae, Ardeidae, Phalacrocoracidae, Anatidae, Ciconiidae, Accipitridae, Falconidae, Phasianidae, Rallidae, Gruidae, Otidae, Scolopacidae, Laridae, Columbidae, Strigidae, Apodidae, Meropidae, Coraciidae, Picidae, Corvidae, Sturnidae, Fringillidae, Alaudidae, Laniidae, Muscicapidae, Turdidae, and Emberizidae); and 20 mammalian (Soricidae, Erinaceidae, Leporidae, Vespertilionidae, Castoridae, Cricetidae,

Muridae, Gliridae, Spalacidae, Sciuridae, Canidae, Ursidae, Mustelidae, Felidae, Phocidae, Cervidae, Suidae, Bovidae, Equidae, and Delphinidae);

- Meghalayan – 79: one chondrichthyan (Selachimorpha fam. indet.); ten actynopterygian families (Acipenseridae, Siluridae, Esocidae, Pleuronectidae, Salmonidae, Anguillidae, Gadidae, Percidae, Cyprinidae, and Leuciscidae); three amphibian (Salamandridae, Bufonidae, and Ranidae); five reptilian (Lacertidae, Colubridae, Viperidae, Testudinidae, and Emydidae); 38 avian (Gaviidae, Podicipedidae, Pelecanidae, Ardeidae, Phalacrocoracidae, Anatidae, Ciconiidae, Accipitridae, Falconidae, Meleagrididae, Phasianidae, Rallidae, Gruidae, Otidae, Recurvirostridae, Charadriidae, Scolopacidae, Burhinidae, Laridae, Pteroclididae, Columbidae, Strigidae, Caprimulgidae, Apodidae, Meropidae, Upupidae, Corvidae, Sturnidae, Passeridae, Fringillidae, Hirundinidae, Aegithalidae, Paridae, Oriolidae, Laniidae, Muscicapidae, Sylviidae, and Turdidae); and 22 mammalian (Erinaceidae, Talpidae, Leporidae, Vespertilionidae, Castoridae, Cricetidae, Sminthidae, Muridae, Gliridae, Spalacidae, Sciuridae, Canidae, Ursidae, Mustelidae, Felidae, Phocidae, Cervidae, Suidae, Bovidae, Camelidae, Equidae, and Delphinidae).

These lists show that the vertebrate fauna was most diversified in the Meghalayan, *i.e.*, in the last 4,200 years.

Genus-Family Index and vertebrate paleobiodiversity in the Quaternary of Bulgaria

Summary data on the taxonomic diversity in the seven subdivisions of the Quaternary are given in Table 1 and Fig. 8. As seen, the Genus-Family Index varies between 2.03 (Northgrippian) and 2.98 (Calabrian). Such differences represent ~47%, a considerably greater richness (in terms of taxonomic diversity) of the Calabrian vertebrate fauna compared to that of the Northgrippian one. This means that, in the Calabrian, the number of genera was a three times greater than that in the Northgrippian, which is an indication of a more diversified paleoenvironment.

New to science taxa of vertebrates from the Quaternary in Bulgaria

As seen, the Quaternary has been a very promising period for the vertebrate paleozoologists. Approximately 2.2% (25 species) of the established taxa in the Bulgarian Quaternary localities belonged to new unknown and undescribed taxa. One genus (*Chau-*

Table 1
Recorded number of taxa and Genus/Family Index of vertebrates in the Quaternary in Bulgaria

Subdivisions of Quaternary	Species	Genera	Families	Orders	Genus/Family Index
Gelasian	155	129	59	21	2.18
Calabrian	255	149	50	21	2.98
Chibanian	171	101	40	17	2.52
Late Pleistocene	285	178	62	23	2.87
Greenlandian	213	144	63	28	2.28
Northgrippian	150	110	54	30	2.03
Meghalayan	246	170	79	39	2.15

Fig. 8. Chronostratigraphic change of the faunal diversity (number of established taxa) of vertebrates in the Quaternary of Bulgaria.

vireria, Boev 1997), 22 species and one subspecies of birds, and two species of mammals have been described from Bulgaria: birds – *Geronticus balcanicus* Boev, 1998, *Aquila kurochkini* Boev, 2013 (Fig. 1a), *Circaetus haemusensis* Boev, 2015 (Fig. 1b), *Gyps bochenskii* Boev, 2010 (Fig. 1c), *Falco bakalovi* Boev, 1999 (Fig. 1d), *Chauvireria balcanica* Boev, 1997 (Fig. 2a), *Chauvireria bulgarica* Boev, 2020, *Lagopus balcanicus* Boev, 1995 (Fig. 2b), *Gallinula balcanica* Boev, 1999 (Fig. 2d), *Porzana botunensis* Boev, 2015 (Fig. 2e), *Actitis balcanica* Boev, 1998 (Fig. 3a), *Pica praepica* Boev, 2021 (Fig. 3c), *Coccothraustes simeonovi* Boev, 1998 (Fig. 3d), *Coccothraustes balcanicus* Boev,

1998, *Loxia patevi* Boev, 1999 (Fig. 3e), *Alauda xerarvensis* Boev, 2012 (Fig. 3f), *Eremophila prealpestris* Boev, 2012 (Fig. 4a), *Galerida bulgarica* Boev, 2012 (Fig. 4b), *Lullula balcanica* Boev, 2012 (Fig. 4c), *Melanocorypha donchevi* Boev, 2012 (Fig. 4d), *Lullula slivnicensis* Boev, 2012, *Regulus bulgaricus* Boev, 1999 (Fig. 5a), *Fulica atra pontica* Boev and Karaivanova, 1998; mammals – *Clethrionomys primitivus* Popov, 2001, *Baranogale balcanica* Spassov, 2001. For some new species for science, described by fossil materials from abroad, some of the first confirmations of their existence have been established in Bulgaria: *Tetrao partium* (Kretzoi, 1962) (Fig. 2c), *Otis* aff. *khosatzkii* Bochenski and Kurochkin, 1987 (Fig. 2f), *Corvus praecorax* Depéret, 1890 and *Apus baranensis* Janossy, 1977 (Fig. 3b).

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the data presented above, it could be concluded that 759 species/taxa (628 species at least) of vertebrates have been established on the present day territory of Bulgaria to date: Chondrichthyes (1); Actinopterygii (34); Amphibia (18); Reptilia (33); Aves (298); and Mammalia (374). The richest fauna has been recorded from the Late Pleistocene (285 taxa) and the Calabrian (255). In the last 2.58 Ma, Bulgaria has lost 32.3% of its former Quaternary vertebrate fauna. At least 245 species and 80 genera have been lost, mainly mammals and birds. Five orders disappeared, including three mammalian (Perissodactyla, Proboscidea, and Primates), and two avian (Otidiformes and Pteroclidiformes). In addition, 16 families and 80 genera of amphibians, reptiles, birds and mammals have been lost:

one is amphibian (Palaeobatrachidae); three avian (Gruidae, Otididae and Pteroclididae); two reptilian (Varanidae and Elapidae); and ten mammalian (Dipodidae, Eomyidae, Hystricidae, Ochotonidae, Hyaenidae, Phocidae, Equidae, Rhinocerotidae, Elephantidae, and Cercopithecidae). After small mammals (mainly Cricetidae; 52 taxa), the composition of bovids (27 taxa) and canids (13 taxa) impoverished in a higher extent. The biggest number of recorded vertebrate families is found in the Greenlandian (63), followed by the Late Pleistocene (62). At order level, the vertebrate fauna in the Meghalayan (39 orders) and the Northgrippian (30), which fall in the s. c. Holocene climatic optimum (~10,000–4,000 BP) was the most varied. One genus, 25 species, and one subspecies have been described as new to the science from the Quaternary localities in Bulgaria. Thus, the Quaternary paleozoology is outlined as one of the most promising fields of vertebrate paleontology in the region of the Balkans.

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APPENDIX

List of the taxa of vertebrates established in the Quaternary localities in Bulgaria (available online at https://www.geologica-balkanica.eu/sites/default/files/supplementary/Boev_Geol_Balc_52-1_2023_Appendix.pdf). References listed below are included in the appendix.

REFERENCES

- Agre, D. 1984. Leskovsko settlement and necropolis in its vicinities, Mihaylovgrad Region. In: Velkov, V. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1983*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Smolyan, 48–49 (in Bulgarian).
- Angelov, S., Doncheva-Petkova, D. 1988. Early medieval necropolis near Topola village, Varna Region. In: Velkov, V. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1987*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Blagoevgrad, 206–207 (in Bulgarian).
- Anonymous, 1906. A contribution to the extinct Diluvial fauna in our country. *Priroda* 4, 70–71 (in Bulgarian).
- Atanasov, I. 1994. Archaeological studies of Tower X 4 of the Kovachevsko Kale fortress, 1993. In: Velkov, V., Katincharov, R. (Eds), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1992–1993*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Veliko Tarnovo, 71–73 (in Bulgarian).
- Atanasov, B., Kulov, I., Gorchik, J., Bineva, V., Etie, J., Velkovski, K., Dimitrova, N., Dimitrov, M., Dzhurkovska, G., Ivanov, S., Ilieva, E., Kop, D., Lepek, M., Marinova, E., Todorova, N., Stoev, D., Uzunov, Zh., Tsvetanov, Y., Stockhammer, P. 2014. Studies in Bresto locality near Banja Village, Razlog Municipality. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1983*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences. TDG Print, Sofia, 115–117 (in Bulgarian).
- Bachvarov, K., Todorova, N., Petrova, V., Katsarov, G., Ilieva, D., Nikolova, N., Popova, T., Taneva, S., Vitezovic, S., Maxwini, K. 2014. Archaeological site near Nova Nadezhda village, Haskovo Municipality (from km 245 + 280 to km 245 + 420 on the route on the railway line Plovdiv-Svilengrad). In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1983*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences. TDG Print, Sofia, 57–60 (in Bulgarian).
- Bachvarov, K., Tonkova, M., Leshtakov, P., Kalchev, P., Karailiev, P., Popova, T., Gyurova, M., Zidarov, P., Maxwini, K., Yaneva, M. 2010. Rescue excavations of ritual complexes from late Neolithic, early Iron, late Iron and the Roman Era at the Sarnevo village, Radnevo Region (object 5, lot 2, HW Thracia, km 226 + 600 - km 226 + 850). In: Gergova, D. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2009*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia 47–51 (in Bulgarian).
- Bacvarov, K., Tsurev, A., Todorova, N., Katsarov, G., Nikolova, N., Gleser, R., Becker, V., Yaneva, M. 2019. The prehistoric settlement site of Nova Nadezhda. In: Popov, H. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2018*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences. Bulged, Sofia, 33–35 (in Bulgarian, English abstract).
- Bakalov, P., Nikolov, I. 1962. *Tertiary Mammals of Bulgaria, 10, Les fossiles de Bulgarie*. Bulgarian Academy of Sciences Academic Press, Sofia, 164 pp. (in Bulgarian, with French and Russian summaries).
- Bakalov, P. 1932. The elephant in Bulgaria. *Priroda i nauka* 1, 2–3 (in Bulgarian).
- Bakardzhiev, S., Valchev, T. 2016. Rescue archaeological excavations of settlement from early and late Iron Age, Roman Period and Medieval period – Site No. 1 on the route of gas pipeline No. 2 to the Republic of Turkey near Lozenets, Yambol Region (1st stage). In: Aladzhev, A. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2015*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Bulgarian Academy

- of Sciences. Multiprint, Sofia, 224–226 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Bartosiewicz, L., Choyke A.M. 1991. Animal remains from the 1970–1972 excavations of Iatrus (Krivina), Bulgaria. *Acta Archaeologica Academiae Scientiarum Hungaricae* 43, 181–209.
- Beech, M., Irving, B. 2007. The fish remains. In: Poulter, A. (Ed.), *Nicopolis Ad Istrum. A Late Roman and Early Byzantine City. The Finds and The Biological Remains*. The Society of Antiquaries of London, Oxbow Books, London, 224–241, <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctvh1dmqz.17>.
- Biernacki A.B., Klenina, E. 2022. The Roman Legionary Camp and Early-Byzantine Town of Novae (Moesia Inferior / Moesia Secunda) after Sixty Years of Research. In: Klenina, E. (Ed.), *Novae. Studies and Materials VIII. Actum Atque Tractatum*. Uniwersytet im Adama Mickiewicza w Poznaniu. Poznan, 9–49.
- Boev, N., Boev, Z. 2018. *Aurochs* (*Bos primigenius Bojanos, 1827*) (*Artiodactyla – Mammalia*) in the *Nature and Culture of Bulgaria*. *ZooNotes. Supplement* 5. University “Paisiy Hilendarski” Academic Press, Plovdiv, 120 pp. (in Bulgarian, with English summary).
- Boev, Z. (in press, a). Elk (*Alces alces* (Linnaeus, 1758)) and Reindeer (*Rangifer tarandus* (Linnaeus, 1758)) in the Pleistocene of Bulgaria. *Lynx*.
- Boev, Z. (in press, c). Avian remains from the Late Neolithic settlement of Hadzhidimitrovo (Yambol Region, SE Bulgaria). In: Petrova, V. (Ed.), *The Late Neolithic settlement of Hadzhidimitrovo (Yambol Region, SE Bulgaria)*. Prof. Marin Drinov Academic Press, Sofia.
- Boev, Z. (in press, d). Fossil record. In: Bautista-Rodríguez, J., Ellis, D. (Eds), *The Golden Eagle Around the World. Biology and Conservation the Golden Eagle Around the World*. Hancock House Publishers Ltd, Surrey, Canada.
- Boev, Z. 1988. First proofs of the existence of the black grouse (*Tetrao tetrax* /L./) (Aves, Tetraonidae) in Bulgaria. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 36, 72–77 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Boev, Z. 1991. The birds of the Roman town of Nicopolis ad Istrum (2nd–6th c. AD) at Nikjup, Lovech Region. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 3, 92–102 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Boev, Z. 1992. Paleornithological studies in Bulgaria. In: Campbell, K.E. (Ed.), *Papers in Avian Paleontology Honoring Pierce Brodkorb: Incorporating the Proceedings of the 2nd International Symposium of the Society of Avian Paleontology and Evolution held at the Natural History Museum of Los Angeles County, Los Angeles, 28–30 September 1988*. Los Angeles, Science Series 36, 459–463.
- Boev, Z. 1993. Neolithic birds from the Prehistoric settlement at Kazanluk. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 4, 57–67 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Boev, Z. 1994. The Late Pleistocene birds. In: Kozłowski, J.K., Laville, H., Ginter, B. (Eds), *Temnata Cave. Excavations in Karlukovo Karst Area, Bulgaria*. Jagellonian University Press, Cracow, 55–86.
- Boev, Z. 1995a. Eneolithic and Early Bronze Age birds from the sunken settlement at Sozopol Bay (Bulgarian Black Sea Coast). *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 5, 51–60.
- Boev, Z. 1995b. Middle Villafranchian birds from Varshets (Western Balkan Range - Bulgaria). *Courier Forschungsinstitut Senckenberg* 181, 259–269.
- Boev, Z. 1996a. Gamefowl in Bulgaria over the last 8,000 years. In: Botev, N. (Sen. Ed.), *Proceedings of the International Union of Game Biologists. XXII Congress “The Game and the Man”*, Pensoft Publishers, Sofia–Moscow–St Petersburg, 398–401.
- Boev, Z. 1996b. The Holocene avifauna of Bulgaria (A review of the ornitho-archaeological studies). *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 6, 59–81.
- Boev, Z. 1996c. Raptors and Owls (Aves: Falconiformes et Strigiformes) in the Archaeological Record of Bulgaria. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 6, 83–92.
- Boev, Z. 1997a. Ornithoarchaeology in Bulgaria: development and results. *Archaeologia bulgarica* 1(2), 71–80.
- Boev, Z. 1997b. The Black Grouse, *Tetrao tetrax* (L., 1758) (Tetraonidae, Aves), a disappeared species in Bulgaria (Paleolithic and Neolithic records). *Anthropozoologica* 25–26, 643–646.
- Boev, Z. 1997c. *Chauvireria balcanica* gen. n., sp. n. (Phasianidae - Galliformes) from the Middle Villafranchian of Western Bulgaria. *Geologica Balcanica* 27 (3–4), 69–78, <https://doi.org/10.52321/GeolBalc.27.3-4.69>.
- Boev, Z. 1997d. Wild Galliform and Gruiform Birds (Aves, Galliformes and Gruiformes) in the Archaeological Record of Bulgaria. *International Journal of Osteoarchaeology* 7 (4), 430–439, [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-1212\(199707/08\)7:4<430::AID-OA356>3.0.CO;2-5](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-1212(199707/08)7:4<430::AID-OA356>3.0.CO;2-5).
- Boev, Z. 1997e. Birds of the Roman settlement Arbanas – 1 near town of Pernik. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 7, p. 28 (in Bulgarian).
- Boev, Z. 1998a. Presence of bald ibises (*Geronticus Wagler, 1832*) (Threskiornithidae - Aves) in the Late Pliocene of Bulgaria. *Geologica Balcanica* 28 (1–2), 45–52, <https://doi.org/10.52321/GeolBalc.28.1-2.45>.
- Boev, Z. 1998b. Sur la présence de la bernache a cou roux *Branta ruficollis* (Pallas, 1769) au Würm en Bulgarie. *Branta* 3, 18–19.
- Boev, Z. 1998c. *Actitis balcanica* sp. n. – a Late Pliocene Sandpiper (Aves: Scolopacidae) from Bulgaria. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 9, 71–77.
- Boev, Z. 1998d. First fossil record of the snowy owl *Nyctea scandiaca* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Aves: Strigidae) from Bulgaria. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 9, 79–86.
- Boev, Z. 1998e. A range fluctuation of Alpine swift (*Apus melba* (L., 1758)) (Apodidae – Aves) in Northern Balkan Peninsula in the Riss-Wurm interglacial. *Biogeographia, Nuova Serie* 19, 213–218, <https://doi.org/10.21426/B6110114>.
- Boev, Z. 1998f. Late Pliocene Hawfinches (*Coccothraustes Brisson, 1760*) (Aves: Fringillidae) from Bulgaria. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 9, 87–99.
- Boev, Z. 1999a. *Neogene and Quaternary birds (Aves) from Bulgaria*. DSc Thesis, National Museum of Natural History, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia, Volume I. Basic Part. 243 pp.; Volume II. Supplement 1–Figures, 135 pp.; Volume II. Supplement 2–Tables, 108 pp. (in Bulgarian).
- Boev, Z. 1999b. On the presence of *Tetrao partium* (Kretzoi, 1962) (Tetraonidae – Galliformes) in the Late Pliocene of Bulgaria. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 10, 85–96.
- Boev, Z. 1999c. *Falco bakalovi* sp. n. – a Late Pliocene falcon (Falconidae, Aves) from Varshets (W Bulgaria). *Geologica Balcanica* 29 (1–2), 131–135, <https://doi.org/10.52321/GeolBalc.29.1-2.131>.
- Boev, Z. 1999d. *Gallinula balcanica* sp. n. (Rallidae: Gruiformes) – a middle villafranchian moorhen from Western Bulgaria. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 51 (1), 43–48.
- Boev, Z. 1999e. Late Pliocene bustards (Aves: Otitidae) from Western Bulgaria. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 10, 97–108.
- Boev, Z. 1999f. Earliest finds of crossbills (genus *Loxia*) (Aves: Fringillidae) from Varshets (NW Bulgaria). *Geologica*

- Balcanica* 29 (3–4), 51–57, <https://doi.org/10.52321/Geol-Balc.29.3-4.51>.
- Boev, Z. 1999g. *Regulus bulgaricus* sp. n. – the first fossil Kinglet (Aves: Sylviidae) from the Late Pliocene of Varshets (W Bulgaria). *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 10, 109–115.
- Boev, Z. 2000a. Additional Material of *Geronticus balcanicus* Boev, 1998, and precision of the age of the type locality. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 52 (2), 53–58.
- Boev, Z. 2000b. Late Pleistocene Avifauna of the Razhishkata Cave, Western Bulgaria. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 12, 71–87.
- Boev, Z. 2000c. Early Pleistocene and Early Holocene avifauna of the Cherdzhenitsa Cave, Northwestern Bulgaria. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 11, 107–116.
- Boev, Z. 2000d. The presence of *Apus baranensis* Janossy, 1977 (Aves: Apodidae) in the Late Pliocene of Bulgaria. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 52 (2), 43–52.
- Boev, Z. 2001a. Late Pleistocene birds from the Kozarnika Cave (Montana District; NW Bulgaria). In: Delchev, P., Shanov, S., Benderev, A. (Eds), *Karst. Proceedings of the First National Conference on Environment and Cultural Heritage in Karst. Vol. I. Earth and Man National Museum, Association of Environment and Cultural Heritage in Karst*, Sofia, 113–128.
- Boev, Z. 2001b. Late Pleistocene and Holocene avifauna from three caves in the vicinity of Tran (Pernik District – W Bulgaria). In: Delchev, P., Shanov, S., Benderev, A. (Eds), *Karst. Proceedings of the First National Conference on Environment and Cultural Heritage in Karst. Vol. I. Earth and Man National Museum, Association of Environment and Cultural Heritage in Karst*, Sofia, 98–106.
- Boev, Z. 2001c. Late Pleistocene and Holocene avian finds from the vicinity of the Lakatnik r/w Station (W Bulgaria). In: Delchev, P., Shanov, S., Benderev, A. (Eds), *Karst. Proceedings of the First National Conference on Environment and Cultural Heritage in Karst. Vol. I. Earth and Man National Museum, Association of Environment and Cultural Heritage in Karst*, Sofia, 107–112.
- Boev, Z. 2001d. Birds over the mammoth's head in Bulgaria. In: Cavaretta, G., Gioia, P., Mussi, M., Palombo, M.R. (Eds), *The World of Elephants*. Proceedings of the 1st International Congress, Rome, 180–186.
- Boev, Z. 2002. Tetraonidae Vigors, 1825 (Galliformes – Aves) in the Neogene–Quaternary record of Bulgaria and the origin and evolution of the family. *Proceedings of the 4th Meeting of the ICAZ Bird Working Group, Krakow*. *Acta Zoologica Cracoviensis* 45 (Special Issue), 263–282.
- Boev, Z. 2003. Distribution of the Little Bustard (*Tetrax tetrax* Linnaeus, 1758) and the Great Bustard (*Otis tarda* Linnaeus, 1758) (Aves: Otididae Gray, 1845) in Bulgaria during the Late Pleistocene and the Holocene. *Annuaire de l'Université de Sofia, Faculté de biologie* 93–94 (1), 41–47.
- Boev, Z. 2004 Middle and Late Holocene birds from the Eastern Late Thracian Plane (S Bulgaria). *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 16, 123–132 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Boev, Z. 2005. Fossil birds in the National Museum of Natural History, Sofia: composition, development and scientific value. *Zoologische Mededelingen* 79 (3), 35–44.
- Boev, Z. 2006a. Pleistocene avifaunas of Bulgaria: a brief review. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 17, 95–107.
- Boev, Z. 2006b. Late Holocene avian remains from the localities of the Roman period in Bulgaria. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 17, 109–123.
- Boev, Z. 2006c. Deuxième trouvaille de la Bernache a cou roux *Branta ruficollis* (Pallas, 1769) (Aves: Anatidae) au Quatenaire en Bulgarie. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 17, p. 124.
- Boev, Z. 2006d. Early Pleistocene avifauna of Kunino (NW Bulgaria). *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 17, 125–132.
- Boev, Z. 2006e. Middle Pleistocene birds from the Morovitsa Cave (Lovech District, NC Bulgaria). In: Zhalov, A., Daaliev, T. (Eds), *Proceedings of the Jubilee Scientific Conference “75 years of Organized Speleology in Bulgaria”*. Bulgarian Federation of Speleology, Sofia, 103–110.
- Boev, Z. 2006f. Avian remains from the Early Bronze Age settlement near Dyadovo village (vicinity of the town of Nova Zagora (Stara Zagora Region, SE Bulgaria). *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 17, 133–135.
- Boev, Z. 2007. Neogene avifaunas of Bulgaria (a brief review). In: Bakardjieva, N., Chankova, S., Krastanov, B., Gateva, S. (Compilers), *Proceedings of the 3rd National Seminar Evolution and Ecology – 2007*. Union of the Scientists of Bulgaria, Sofia, 26–35.
- Boev, Z. 2008. First finds of megantereon discovered in Bulgaria. In: Popov, A., Slavova, S. (Eds), *Новосты – News 2007*. Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia, 104–107.
- Boev, Z. 2009a. Avian remains from the Early Neolithic settlement of Slatina (Present Sofia City, Bulgaria). *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 61 (2), 151–156.
- Boev, Z. 2009b. Avian remains from the Early Chalcolithic settlement in Burgas (SE Bulgaria). *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 61 (2), 157–160.
- Boev, Z. 2009c. Avian remains from the Early Neolithic rettlement near Yabalkovo Village (Haskovo Region, South-East Bulgaria). *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 61 (3), 317–322.
- Boev, Z. 2009d. Avian remains from the Late Chalcolithic settlement near Hotnitsa Village (Veliko Tarnovo Region, CN Bulgaria). *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 61 (1), 49–54.
- Boev, Z. 2010. *Gyps bochenskii* sp. n. (Aves: Falconiformes) from the Late Pliocene of Varshets (NW Bulgaria). *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 62 (2), 211–242.
- Boev, Z. 2011a. Exploration of the Neogene Birds of Bulgaria – achievements, conclusions and perspectives. In: Batashev, M.S., Makarov, N.P., Martinovich, N.V. (Eds), *Honoring Arkadiy Yakovlevich Tugarinov. A Selection of Scientific Papers*. Krasnoyarsk Region Regional Museum, Krasnoyarsk, 35–43.
- Boev, Z. 2011b. New fossil record of the Late Pliocene kestrel (*Falco bakalovi* Boev, 1999) from the type locality in Bulgaria. *Geologica Balcanica* 40 (1–3), 13–30, <https://doi.org/10.52321/GeolBalc.40.1-3.13>.
- Boev, Z. 2012a. Sub-recent avian remains from two cave localities of the Devetashko Plateau (Lovech Region, CN Bulgaria). *ZooNotes* 31, 1–3.
- Boev, Z. 2012b. Neogene Larks (Aves: Alaudidae (Vigors, 1825)) from Bulgaria. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 64 (3), 295–318.
- Boev, Z. 2013. Avian remains from the Late Neolithic settlement of Sarnevo (Stara Zagora Region, SC Bulgaria) *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 65 (2), 259–262.
- Boev, Z. 2014a. Animal remains of the Middle Neolithic settlement near Krum Village (Haskovo Region (SE Bulgaria). *ZooNotes* 58, 1–6.
- Boev, Z. 2014b. Animal remains of the Late Antiquity settlement near Dyakovo Village (Kyustendil Region (SW Bulgaria). *ZooNotes* 65, 1–7.
- Boev, Z. 2015a. An Early Pleistocene Snake-eagle (*Circaetus haemusensis* sp. n. – Aves, Accipitriformes) from Varshets (NW Bulgaria). *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 67 (1), 127–138.

- Boev, Z. 2015a. Fossil and subfossil remains of birds and mammals from the Mirizlivka cave (Vidin Region – NW Bulgaria). *ZooNotes* 75, 1–3.
- Boev, Z. 2015c. *Porzana botunensis* sp. n., a new Early Pleistocene Crane (Aves Rallidae) from Bulgaria. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 67 (2), 283–290.
- Boev, Z. 2016a. Subfossil vertebrate fauna from Forum Serdica (Sofia, Bulgaria), 16th–18th century. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 68 (3), 415–424.
- Boev, Z. 2016b. Paleobiodiversity of the Vrachanska Mountains in the Villafranchian: a case study of the Varshets (Dolno Ozirovo) Early Pleistocene locality of fossil fauna and flora. In: Bechev, D., Georgiev, D. (Eds), *Faunistic Diversity of Vrachanski Balkan Nature Park*, *ZooNotes*, Supplement 3. Plovdiv University Press, Plovdiv, 299–323.
- Boev, Z. 2016c. New animal remains from Pliska, the medieval capital (10 c. AD) of Bulgaria, (Shumen Region, NE Bulgaria). *ZooNotes* 87, 1–3.
- Boev, Z. 2017a. Fossil and Subfossil Record of Species of the Genus *Lynx* Kerr, 1792 (Mammalia: Felidae) in Bulgaria. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 69 (3), 303–306.
- Boev, Z. 2017b. Fossil and subfossil record of Reptiles (Reptilia Laurenti, 1768) in Bulgaria. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 24, 165–178.
- Boev, Z. 2017c. New data on the subfossil fauna from “Forum Serdica” (Sofia City, Bulgaria; 3–19th century A. D.). *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 24, 179–186.
- Boev, Z. 2017d. Avian finds from the Early Neolithic settlement near Kapitan-Dimitriev village (Pazardzhik Region). *ZooNotes* 112, 1–3.
- Boev, Z. 2017e. Late Neolithic and Late Antiquity avian finds of Chavdarova Cheshma (Simeonovgrad, Haskovo Region). *ZooNotes* 111, 1–3.
- Boev, Z. 2017f. Bone remains of the Late Antiquity – Early Medieval deposits of the National Academy of Art (Sofia, Bulgaria). *Bulletin of the Natural History Museum – Plovdiv* 2, 9–11.
- Boev, Z. 2017g. Fossil records of Rhinoceroses (Rhinocerotidae Gray, 1821), Chalicotheres (Chalicotherioidea Gill, 1872) and Brontotheres (Brontotherioidea (Marsh, 1873) (Perissodactyla Owen, 1848 – Mammalia Linnaeus, 1758) in Bulgaria. *Bulletin of the Natural History Museum – Plovdiv* 2, 1–7.
- Boev, Z. 2018a. Past distribution of *Monachus monachus* in Bulgaria – subfossil and historical records (Carnivora: Phocidae). *Lynx* 49 (1), 163–176, <https://doi.org/10.2478/lynx-2018-0013>.
- Boev, Z. 2018b. Subfossil fauna from “Forum Serdica” (Sofia City, Bulgaria) of Antiquity (2nd – 4th century AD) and Ottoman Epoch (15th–18th century AD) (Excavations 2017). *Bulletin of the Natural History Museum – Plovdiv* 3, 7–13.
- Boev, Z. 2018c. Fossil and subfossil record of vertebrate animals (Vertebrata J.-B. Lamarck, 1801) along the Western Black Sea Coast (Bulgaria). In: Peev, D. et al. (Eds), *Proceedings of the First European Symposium “Research, Conservation and Management of Biodiversity of European Seashores” (RCMBES)*. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica*, Supplement 11, 105–110.
- Boev, Z. 2018d. Birds in everyday life and art in Bulgaria (Thracian and Roman periods). *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 27, 3–39.
- Boev, Z. 2019a. Fossil record of the Irish Elk (*Megaloceros giganteus* (Blumenbach, 1799)) (Artiodactyla: Cervidae) in Bulgaria. *Bulletin of the Natural History Museum – Plovdiv* 4, 27–31.
- Boev, Z. 2019b. Past distribution of *Camelus bactrianus* and *Camelus dromedarius* in Bulgaria: subfossil record (Artiodactyla: Camelidae). *Lynx* 50, 29–36.
- Boev, Z. 2019c. The Eurasian Collared Dove (*Streptopelia decaocto* Frivaldszky, 1838) – a subrecent invasive species of the avifauna of Bulgaria (subfossil records). *ZooNotes* 141, 1–3.
- Boev, Z. 2019d. Late Pleistocene avifauna of Nanin Kamak Cave (CN Bulgaria). *Bulletin of the Natural History Museum – Plovdiv* 4, 21–25.
- Boev, Z. 2019e. Late Antiquity (3–5 century A. D.) Fauna from Building Excavations on Exarch Joseph Street (Sofia City, Bulgaria). *Bulletin of the Natural History Museum – Plovdiv* 4, 1–8.
- Boev, Z. 2019f. Animal remains of the medieval settlement near Brankovtsi village (Vidin Region, NW Bulgaria). *ZooNotes* 148, 1–4.
- Boev, Z. 2019g. Late Antiquity animal remains of the military settlement near Barkach village (Pleven Region, CN Bulgaria). *ZooNotes* 145, 1–3.
- Boev, Z. 2020a. Late Pleistocene *Crocota crocota spelaea* in Bulgaria: distribution and history of research (Carnivora: Hyaenidae). *Lynx* 51, 19–29, <https://doi.org/10.37520/lynx.2020.002>.
- Boev, Z. 2020b. Past distribution of *Ursus arctos* in Bulgaria: fossil and subfossil records (Carnivora: Ursidae). *Lynx* 51, 5–18, <https://doi.org/10.37520/lynx.2020.001>.
- Boev, Z. 2020c. Fossil and subfossil records of Shrikes (Laniidae Swainson, 1824 – Passeriformes Linnaeus, 1758) in Bulgaria. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 41, 77–81, <https://doi.org/10.48027/hnb.41.10001>.
- Boev, Z. 2020d. New Data on the Fauna of the Late Antiquity Northern Fortification Walls of Serdica (3rd–6th century A. D.) from Building Excavations on Exarch Joseph Street (Sofia, Bulgaria). *Bulletin of the Natural History Museum – Plovdiv* 5, 15–23.
- Boev, Z. 2020e. *Chauvireria bulgarica* sp. n. – an extinct Early Pleistocene small phasianid of Phasianinae Horsfield, 1821 from Bulgaria. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 41, 55–70, <https://doi.org/10.48027/hnb.41.08001>.
- Boev, Z. 2021a. *Coelodonta antiquitatis* in the Pleistocene of Bulgaria (Perissodactyla: Rhinocerotidae). *Lynx* 52, 55–62, <https://doi.org/10.37520/lynx.2021.004>.
- Boev, Z. 2021b. Last aurochs (*Bos primigenius* Bojanus, 1827) have survived in Bulgaria. *Lynx* 52, 139–142, <https://doi.org/10.37520/lynx.2021.010>.
- Boev, Z. 2021c. Fossil amphibians in Bulgaria. *Priroda* 2, 92–96 (in Bulgarian).
- Boev, Z. 2021d. Animal remains of the medieval settlement near Petarch village (Sofia Province, CW Bulgaria). *ZooNotes* 184, 1–4.
- Boev, Z. 2021e. An Early Pleistocene magpie (*Pica praepica* sp. n.) (Corvidae Leach, 1820) from Bulgaria. *Bulletin of the Natural History Museum – Plovdiv* 6, 51–59.
- Boev, Z. 2022a. Alpine ibex (*Capra ibex* Linnaeus, 1758) in Bulgaria – fossil record, distribution and disappearance. *Bulletin of the Natural History Museum – Plovdiv* 7, 13–20.
- Boev, Z. 2022b. Animal remains of the Late Antiquity settlement (3rd–6th century A. D.) near Shipot village (Vidin Region, NW Bulgaria). *Bulletin of the Natural History Museum – Plovdiv* 7, 5–11.
- Boev, Z. 2022c. Avian remains from the Palace Center and the Citadel of the medieval capital Pliska of Bulgaria (10th century AD). *ZooNotes* 195, 1–4.

- Boev, Z. 2022d. Past Distribution of the Red Deer (*Cervus elaphus* Linnaeus, 1758) (Cervidae, Mammalia) in Bulgaria. *Bulletin of the Natural History Museum – Plovdiv* 7, 27–48.
- Boev, Z., Popgeorgiev, G. 2021. Animal remains of the medieval settlement (9th–10th century A.D.) near Nedan village (Veliko Tarnovo Region, CN Bulgaria). *ZooNotes* 170, 1–4.
- Boev, Z., Spassov, N. 2019. Past distribution of *Castor fiber* in Bulgaria: fossil, subfossil and historical records (Rodentia: Castoridae). *Lynx* 50, 37–49, <https://doi.org/10.2478/lynx-2018-0013>.
- Boev, Z. 2002. Neogene avifauna of Bulgaria. In: Zhou, Z., Zhang, F. (Eds), *Proceedings of the 5th Symposium of the Society of Avian Palaeontology and Evolution*. Science Press, Beijing, 29–40.
- Boev, Z. 2013. *Aquila kurochkini* sp. n., a New Late Pliocene Eagle (Aves, Accipitriformes) from Varshets (NW Bulgaria). *Paleontological Journal* 47 (11), 1344–1354, <https://doi.org/10.1134/S003103011311004X>.
- Boev, Z. 2014. Late Holocene distribution of the European Shag (*Phalacrocorax aristotelis* (Linnaeus, 1761) in Bulgaria. *ZooNotes* 54, 1–3.
- Boev, Z. 2022b. European bison (*Bison bonasus* Linnaeus, 1758) in Bulgaria – fossil and historical records, distribution and disappearance. *Journal of Wildlife and Biodiversity* 6, 1–8.
- Boev, Z., Milchev, B., Popov, V. 2007. Fauna, Zoogeography, and Ecology of Birds in Bulgaria. In: Fet, V., Popov, A. (Eds), *Biogeography and Ecology of Bulgaria*. Springer, Dordrecht, 39–84, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-5781-6_3.
- Boev, Z., Beech, M. 2007. The Bird Bones. In: Poulter, A.G. (Ed.), *Nicopolis Ad Istrum. A Late Roman and Early Byzantine City. The Finds and the Biological Remains*. The Society of Antiquaries of London, Oxbow Books, London, 242–253 + 307–318, <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctvh1dmqz.18>.
- Boev, Z., Gerasimov, G., Iankov, P. 2007. *Phasianus colchicus colchicus* (Colchic) Pheasant. In: Iankov, P. (Ed.), *Atlas of Breeding Birds in Bulgaria*. Bulgarian Society for the Protection of Birds, Conservation Series, Book 10. Bulgarian Society for the Protection of Birds, Sofia, 204–205.
- Boev, Z., Iliev, N. 1989. Les oiseaux dans la nourriture de la population de la ville intérieure de Veliki Preslav (IXe–Xe s.). *Arheologiya* 4, 40–43 (in Bulgarian, with French abstract).
- Boev, Z., Iliev, N. 1991. Les oiseaux et leur importance pour les habitants de Veliki Preslav (IXe—Xe s.). *Arheologiya* 3, 43–48 (in Bulgarian, with French abstract).
- Boev, Z., Karaivanova, E. 1998. *Fulica atra pontica* subsp. n. from the Middle Holocene on the South Black Sea Coast, Bulgaria. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 9, 53–69.
- Boev, Z., Mikkola, H. 2022. First Pleistocene record of Great Grey Owl (*Strix nebulosa* Forster, 1772) in Bulgaria. *Comptes rendus de l'Académie bulgare des Sciences* 75 (5), 680–685, <https://doi.org/10.7546/CRABS.2022.05.07>.
- Boev, Z., Ribarov, G. 1990. La faune ornithologique de la localité sombreée pres d'Urdoviza (actuellement Kiten) de l'Âge du bronze recent. *Arheologiya* 2, 53–57 (in Bulgarian, with French abstract).
- Boev, Z., Ribarov, G. 1993. Birds from the ancient town of Kabyle (1st millenium B.C. – 6th century A.D.) near Kabyle. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 4, 68–77 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Boev, Z., Spassov, N. (in press). Formation of the recent terrestrial fauna of Bulgaria. In: Zhelezov, G. (Chief Ed.), *Geography of Bulgaria*. Prof. Marin Drinov Academic Publishing Housre, Sofia (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Boev, Z., Stallibrass, S. 2020. Avian remains from the Thracian trade settlement Pistiros (5–2 c. BC) near Vetren, Pazardzhik Province, SC Bulgaria). *Bulletin of the Natural History Museum – Plovdiv* 5, 43–47.
- Bonchev, G. 1900. La grotte du village Goliama-Jéliezna (arrondissement de Troyan). *Travaux de Société bulgare des sciences naturelles* 1, 80–98 (in Bulgarian, with French abstract).
- Bonev, A., Aleksandrov, G. 1991. Thracian cult center “Bagachina”, Mihaylovgrad Region. In: Bonev, A. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1990*. National Institute of Arceology and Museum, Lovech, p. 63 (in Bulgarian).
- Borislavov, B. 2012. Settlement of the Bronze Age in the Badema locality near Izvorovo village, Harmanli Municipality. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2011*. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 125–127 (in Bulgarian).
- Borislavov, B., Hristov, M., Handzhiiska-Yankulova, V. 2016. Belantash rock sanctuary near Vrata village, Asenovgrad municipality, Plovdiv Region. In: Aladzhev, A. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2015*. National Institute of Arceology and Museum. Multiprint, Sofia, 194–197 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Boudadi-Maligne, M. 2009. Les loups (*Canis lupus*) des niveaux paléolithiques supérieurs des grottes de Kozarnika (Gara Orechets) et de Redaka II. Approche paléontologique et taphonomique. In: Gatsov, I., Guadelli, J.-L. (Eds), *Saxa Loquuntur. Volume in Honour of the 65th Anniversary of Nikolay Sirakov*. Avalon, Sofia, 109–117.
- Boyadzhiev, Y., Boyadzhiev, K., Petrov, V. 2013. Exploration of the Yunatsite settlement mound. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2012*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Kolbis Publishing House, Sofia, 88–90 (in Bulgarian).
- Boyadzhiev, Y., Boyadzhiev, K. 2011. Chalcolithic settlement “Varhari”. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2010*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 95–98 (in Bulgarian).
- Boyanov, I. 2012. Archaeological study in the Deninata Plocha locality near Mirkovo village, Municipality of Mirkovo. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2011*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 328–331 (in Bulgarian).
- Chernakov, D. 2011. Archaeological excavations of a Chalcolithic necropolis near the Kosharna village in the “Koru Gyodzhluk” Locality. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2010*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 81–83 (in Bulgarian).
- Chernakov, S., Gurova, M. 2013. Archaeological excavations of the settlement mound near the Bazovets village, Dve Mogili Municipality. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2012*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Kolbis Publishing House, Sofia, 64–67 (in Bulgarian).
- Chichikova, M. 1983. Thracian tsar’s tomb near Sveshtari village, Razgrad Region. In: Velkov, V. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1982*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Plevan, 42–44 (in Bulgarian).

- Chichikova, M., Dimitrov, K., 2016. *Seutopolis, the Town of Seuth III*. Multiprint, Kostinbrod, 204 pp. (in Bulgarian).
- Chohadzhiiev, M. 1980. Excavations of the prehistoric settlement in the "Lenin" Quarter of town of Pernik. In: Velkov, V., Katincharov, R. (Eds), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1979*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Haskovo, 40–41 (in Bulgarian).
- Cholakov, D., Raycheva, M. 2019. Excavations of 'late Antique production complex and early Medieval settlement' site in the territory of Mirovyane village, Sofia Capital Municipality. In: Popov, H. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2018*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Bulged, Sofia, 382–385 (in Bulgarian, English abstract).
- Cholakov, I., Raycheva, M. 2017. Excavations of the "Late Antique production complex and early Medieval settlement" site in the territory of Mirovyane village, Sofia Capital Municipality. In: Vagalinski, L. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2016*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Bulged, Sofia, 437–441 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Cholakov, I., Raycheva, M. 2018. Excavations of "Late Antique production complex and early Medieval settlement" site near Mirovyane village, Sofia Capital Municipality. In: Vagalinski, L. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2017*. BAS, National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Bulged, Sofia, 380–384 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Chukalev, K., Rabovyanov, D., Aleksandrova, S., Uzunov, Z., Dermendzhiev, E., Elenski, N. 2012. Searches for archaeological sites along the Nabucco Gas Pipeline route, Sector 4. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2011*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 589–591 (in Bulgarian).
- Cohen, K.M., Finney, S.C., Gibbard, P.L., Fan, J.-X. 2013. The ICS International Chronostratigraphic Chart. *Episodes* 36 (3), 199–204. <https://doi.org/10.18814/epiiugs/2013/v36i3/002>.
- Cregut-Bonnoure, E., Spassov, N. 2002. *Hemitragus orientalis* nov. sp. (Mammalia, Bovidae, Caprinae), un nouveau taxon d'Europe orientale. *Revue de paléobiologie* 21 (2), 553–573.
- Damyanyov, D., Boyadzhiev, N. 2010. Rescue archaeological research in the Uleya Cave near Mogilitsa village, Municipality of Smolyan. In: Gergova, D. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2009*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 192–194 (in Bulgarian).
- Damyanyov, D., Boyadzhiev, N. 2012. Archaeological study of Uleya cave, in the land of the Mogilits village, Municipality of Smolyan. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2011*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 499–501 (in Bulgarian).
- Delpech, F., Guadelli, J.-L. 1992. Les grandes Mammifères gravettiens et aurignaciens de la grotte de Temnata. In: Kozłowski J.K., Laville, H., Ginter, B. (Eds), *Temnata Cave. Excavations in Karlukovo Karst Area, Bulgaria*. Vol. 1, Part. I. Jagellonian University, Cracow, 141–216.
- Delpech, F., Guadelli, J.-L. 1991. Quelques aspects de l'archéozoologie d'après les faunes de la grotte de Temnata à Karloukovo (Bulgarie du Nord). *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 3, 103–110.
- Dimitrov, B., Avramova, M., 1994. Chalcolithic and Bronze Age finds in the aquatory of the Sozopol Bay. In: Velkov, V., Katincharov, R. (Eds), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1992-1993*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Veliko Tarnovo, 20–21 (in Bulgarian).
- Dimitrov, I. 1985. Exploration of the early Medieval Bulgarian necropolis in Balchik. In: Velkov, V. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1984*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Sliven, p. 268 (in Bulgarian).
- Dzhambazov, N., 1955b. New data on the exploration of the Paleolithic along the valley of Iskar River. *Priroda i znanie* 2, 23–24 (in Bulgarian).
- Dzhambazov, N. 1957. First inhabitants of our country. In: Dzhambazov, N. et al. (Eds), *Archaeological discoveries in Bulgaria*. Narodna Prosveta, Sofia, 7–29 (in Bulgarian).
- Dzhambazov, N., 1959. New data towards the study of the Paleolithic culture in the Pobitite kamani (Dikilitash). *Priroda i znanie* 1, 20–23 (in Bulgarian).
- Dzhambazov, N. 1952. New Paleolithic locality in Bulgaria – the Pesht Cave. *Priroda i znanie* 7, 19–21 (in Bulgarian).
- Dzhambazov, N. 1953. New studies of the caves along the valley of Osam river. *Priroda i znanie* 3, 22–24 (in Bulgarian).
- Dzhambazov, N. 1954. Lovech caves. *Priroda i znanie* 2, 17–19 (in Bulgarian).
- Dzhambazov, N. 1955a. Hunt and fishery of the primitive man in our lands. *Lov i ribolov* 5, 2–3 (in Bulgarian).
- Dzhambazov, N. 1960. Parnika Cave near Bezhanovo village (Lovech Region). *Arheologiya* 4, 54–58 (in Bulgarian).
- Dzhambazov, N. 1981. Ossements d'animaux. In: Georgiev, G., Čičikova, M. (Eds), *Samouilitsa 2. Cultures préhistoriques en Bulgarie*. Bulletin de l'Institut d'archéologie 36, 54–57.
- Dzhambazov, N., Sirakov, N., Sirakova, S., Ivanova, S., Gatsov, I. 1977. Excavations in the Bacho Kiro Cave near the Dryanovo monastery. In: Velkov, V., Katincharov, R. (Eds), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1976*. Proceedings of the 22nd National Archeological Conference. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Regional Historical Museum Ruse, 12–13 (in Bulgarian).
- Dzhebir, G., Yordanov, G., Yankova, I., Sirakova, D., Petrova, M., Neov, B., Hristov, P., Radoslavov, G., Hristova, L., Spassov, N. 2018. Comparative genetic analysis of subfossil wild horses (from the Neolithic Age and Early Bronze Age) and present-day domestic horses from Bulgaria. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 25, 3–10.
- Elenski, N. 2017. Archaeological excavations of the early Neolithic settlement Dzhulyunitsa - Smardesh. In: Vagalinski, L. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2016*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Bulged, Sofia, 56–59 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Fernandez, P. 2009. Mammalian dynamics and palaeoecological analysis during the Pleistocene in Kozarnika Cave (Bulgaria). In: Gatsov, I., Guadelli, J.-L. (Ed.), *Saxa Loquuntur. Volume in Honour of the 65th Anniversary of Nikolay Sirakov*. Avalon Publishing House, Sofia, 59–73.
- Frémondeau, D., Ottoni, C., Ivanova, S., Marinova, E., Spassov, N., Hristova, L., Konyovska, R., Van Neer, W., Lupianez, N., Gurova, M. 2020. New mtDNA and isotopic evidence on Late Pleistocene cave bears in the Balkans: the case study of Magura Cave, NW Bulgaria. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 1–18.
- Ganetsovski, G. 2012. Rescue archaeological excavations of the Early Neolithic settlement in Valoga (Dolnita Laki) locality near Ohoden village (Vratsa Region). In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2011*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 43–45 (in Bulgarian).

- Georgiev, D., Stoycheva, S. 2010. New Late Pleistocene locality of the Alpine IbeX (*Capra ibex* L.) (Mammalia: Bovidae) in Bulgaria. *ZooNotes* 14, 1–4.
- Georgiev, D., Yankov, L., Stoycheva, S., Delev, S., Zhelev, P., Pavlova, A., Zagorska, M. 2010. New localities of Quaternary fossil bears (*Ursus* sp. L.) (Mammalia: Carnivora: Ursidae). *ZooNotes* 8, 1–4.
- Georgiev, D., Yankov, L., Tanev, T., Kostov, D., Madzharov, T., Dilovski, G. 2014. New Quaternary remains of terrestrial vertebrates of some caves in Bulgaria. *ZooNotes* 63, 1–3.
- Gergova, D., Balkanska, A., Valcheva, D., Mihaylova, Zh., Mateva, B. 1990. In: Velkov, V. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1989*. Committee of Culture, Kyustendil, 46–49 (in Bulgarian).
- Gergova, D., Ivanov, Y., Dermendzhiev, N., Radoslavova, G., Tankova, V., Hristova, R. 2010. Rescue excavations of site 36, hw “Trakia”, lot 4, near the village of Dragantsi, municipality of Karnobat. In: Gergova, D. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2009*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 119–123 (in Bulgarian).
- Grgbska-Kulow, M., Zidarov, P., Vasilev, I., Suvandzhiev, I., Marinova-Wolf, E., de Cupere, B. 2016. Excavations at Ilindentsi-Masovets Neolithic site in Southwestern Bulgaria. In: Aladzhov, A. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2015*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Multiprint, Sofia, 68–72 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Grigorov, V. 2012. Pliska “Palace Center – East”. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2011*. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 385–387 (in Bulgarian).
- Guadelli, A., Guadelli, J.-L., Sirakov, N., Krumov, I., Mitov, K. 2015. Late Paleolithic studies in the Redaka II Cave, Belogradchik Region. In: Kabakchieva, G. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2014*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Smolyan, 30–31 (in Bulgarian).
- Guadelli, A., Boyadzhiev, K., Guadelli, J.-L., Crevcoeur, I., Karastoyanova, N. 2014. A. Manastira Cave, Veliko Tarnovo Province. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2013*. TDG Print, Sofia, 29–31 (in Bulgarian).
- Guadelli, A., Boyadzhiev, K., Guadelli, J.-L. 2016. Excavations in Golyamata Peshtera (Veliko Tarnovo) in 2015. In: Aladzhov, A. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2015*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Multiprint, Sofia, 91–94 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Guadelli, A., Boyadzhiev, K., Guadelli, J.-L., Mitov, K., Krevkyor, I. 2013. Rescue excavations in the Manastira Cave. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2012*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Kolbis Publishing House, Sofia, 32–33 (in Bulgarian).
- Guadelli, A., Boyadzhiev, K., Guadelli, J.-L., Sirakov, N. 2013. Searches for cave dwellings in land of the villages Samovodene, Belyakovets and Hotnitsa, Veliko Tarnovo Municipality. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2012*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Kolbis Publishing House, Sofia, 514–517 (in Bulgarian).
- Guadelli, A., Guadelli, J.-L., Simov, N., Karastoyanova, N., Mitov, K., Krumov, I., Taneva, S. 2019. No 3. Middle and Late Paleolithic deposits in the Redaka 2 Cave. In: Popov, H. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2018*. Bulged, Sofia, 7–9 (in Bulgarian).
- Guadelli, A., Guadelli, J.-L., Krumov, I., Sirakov, N. 2011. Drilling research in the Redaka II Cave. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2010*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 25–28 (in Bulgarian).
- Guadelli, A., Guadelli, J.-L., Simov, N., Karastoyanova, N., Mitov, K., Krumov, I., Taneva, S. 2019. Middle and Late Paleolithic deposits in Redaka II Cave. In: Popov, H. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2018*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Bulged, Sofia, 7–9 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Guadelli, A., Guadelli, J.-L., Sirakov, N., Krumov, I., Mitov, K. 2014b. Investigation of the Paleolithic in the Redaka II Cave, Belogradchik Province. In: Kabakchieva, G. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2013*. Aktiv Komers, Sofia, 30–31 (in Bulgarian).
- Guadelli, A., Guadelli, J.-L., Sirakov, N., Krumov, I., Mitov, K. 2013. Paleolithic studies in the Redaka Cave II. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2012*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Kolbis Publishing House, Sofia, 30–31 (in Bulgarian).
- Guadelli, A., Guadelli, J.-L., Sirakov, N., Krumov, I., Mitov, K. 2014. Studies of the Paleolithic in the Redaka Cave II, Belogradchik region. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1983*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. TDG Print, Sofia, 26–29 (in Bulgarian).
- Guadelli, A., Sirakov, N., Guadelli, J.-L., Fernandez, P. 2010. Drilling examination in the Redaka II Cave, Belogradchik Region: middle and late Paleolithic. In: Gergova, D. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2009*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 26–29 (in Bulgarian).
- Guadelli, J.-L., Delpech, F. 2000. Les grands mammifères du début du paléolithique supérieur à Temnata. In: Ginter, B., Kozłowski, J.K., Guadelli, J.-L., Laville, H. (Eds), *Excavation in Karlukovo Karst Area, Bulgaria*. 2.1, Jagellonian University, Cracow, 53–158.
- Guadelli, J.-L. 2009. Les félins de la grotte Kozarnika (Bulgarie du Nordouest). Résultats préliminaires. In: Gatsov I., Guadelli J.-L. (Eds), *Saxa Loquuntur. Volume in Honour of the 65th Anniversary of Nikolay Sirakov*. Avalon, Sofia, 75–100.
- Guadelli, J.-L., Delpeche, F., Guadelli, A., Miteva, V. 1999. Etude de la faune des niveaux gravettiens de la Crotte Kozarnika (Bulgarie du Nord): résultats préliminaires. *Koziologia Bulgarica* 3 (2), 1–14.
- Guadelli, J.-L., Sirakov, N., Ivanova, S., Sirakova, S., Anastasova, E., Courtaud, P., Dimitrova, I., Djabarska, N., Fernandez, P., Ferrier, C., Fontugne, M., Gambier, D., Guadelli, A., Iordanova, D., Iordanova, N., Kovatcheva, M., Krumov, I., Leblanc, J.-C., Mallye, J.-B., Marinska, M., Miteva, V., Popov, V., Spassov, R., Taneva, S., Tisterat-Laborde, N., Tsanova, T. 2005. Une séquence du paléolithique inférieur au paléolithique récent dans les Balkans: la grotte Kozarnika à Orechets (Nord-Ouest de la Bulgarie). In: Molines, N., Moncel, M.-H., Monnier, J.-L. (Eds), *British Archaeological Reports, International Series* 1364, 87–103.
- Guadelli, J.-L., Sirakov, N., Sirakova, S., Ivanova, S., Popov, V., Fernandez, P., Taneva, S., Dimitrova, I. 2011. Studies of the multilayer archaeological sequence from the Pleistocene in the Kozarnika Cave: Early, Middle and Late Paleolithic. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2010*. Avangard, Sofia, 596 pp. (in Bulgarian).

- Gurova, G., Ivanova, S., Spassov, N., Hristova, L., Popov, V., Marinova, E., Bohme, M. 2017. Excavations at Mishin Kamik Cave: 2016 Season. In: Vagalinski, L. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2016*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Bulged, Sofia, 48–50 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Gurova, M., Ivanova, S., Krumov, I., Spassov, N., Christova, L., Dojar, C. 2015. Study of the Mishin Kamak Cave – Season 2. In: Kabakchieva, G. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2014*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Smolyan, 32–33 (in Bulgarian).
- Gurova, M., Ivanova, S., Marinova, E., Popov, V., Spassov, N., Hristova, L., Verheyden, S., Burlet, C. 2018. Excavations at Mishin Kamik Cave – 2017 Season. In: Vagalinski, L. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2017*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Bulged, Sofia, 8–11 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Gurova, M., Ivanova, S., Spassov, N., Hristova, L., Krumov, I., Verheyden, S., Marinova, E., Dedov, I. 2016. Excavations at Misin Kamik Cave: 2015 season. In: Aladzov, A. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2015*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Multiptint, Sofia, 56–59 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Gurova, M., Ivanova, S., Spassov, N., Hristova, L., Popov, V., Marinova, E., Bohme, M. 2017. Excavations at Mishin Kamik Cave: 2016 season. In: Vagalinski, L. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2016*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Bulged, Sofia, 48–50 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Hlebarov, V. 2004. Cave No. 5 – dwelling of Paleolithic man. *Balgarski drevnosti* 1, 5–6 (in Bulgarian).
- Horacek, I. 1982. Notes on the glacial-time environment in Northern Bulgaria. *Ceskoslovensky kras* 32, 95–103.
- Ignatov, V., Gospodinov, K., Borisova, S. 2014. Regular archaeological survey of a site Burial “eastern” mound, near Karanovo village, Nova Zagora Municipality. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1983*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. TDG Print, Sofia, 205–207 (in Bulgarian).
- Iliev, N. 1997. Remains of a stenoroid horse from the end of Early Pleistocene from Varbeshnitsa Village, Distr. Montana (Bulgaria). *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 8, 121–125 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Iliev, S. 2019. Rescue archaeological excavations in ZP 36110.31.111 and 36110.31.112, Kyuchuk Cheir Locality in the village of Kapitan Andreevo, Svilengrad Municipality. In: Popov, H. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2018*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Bulged, Sofia, 122–124 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Iliev, N., Boev, Z. 1990. Birds in the food of the inhabitants of the outer town of Veliki Preslav (9–10th century). *Interdisciplinarni Izsledvaniya, National Institute of Archeology and Museum* 17, 91–94 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Iliev, N., Boev, Z., Spassov, N. 1992. Restes osseux d’animaux de la villa de l’époque antique basse et de la localité de l’époque haute byzantine dans le quartier Béla voda, district de Pernik. *Arheologiya* 1, 44–53 (in Bulgarian, with French abstract).
- Iliev, N., Boev, Z., Spassov, N. 1993. Ossements d’animaux de la ville romaine de Ratiaria (IIe–IVe s.) près d’Arcar, village de la région de Montana. *Arheologiya* 4, 52–59 (in Bulgarian, with French abstract).
- Ishirkov, A. 1921. Water buffalo in Bulgaria. Biogeographical notes. *Estestvoznaniye i geografiya* 9–10, 232–349 (in Bulgarian).
- Ivanov, B., Iankov, P., Boev, Z., Georgiev, D., Profirov, L., Dimitrov, M. 2015. List of the birds recorded in Bulgaria (Bulgarian List), 31 December 2014, (1–23), <http://www.bunarco.org/bg/dokladi.html>.
- Ivanov, B., Iankov, P., Profirov, L., Georgiev, D., Dimitrov, M. 2020. *Bulgarian National Rarities Committee. Report No. 1*, 33 pp. (in Bulgarian), https://www.researchgate.net/publication/349140726_Bulgarian_National_Rarities_Committee_Report_No_1.
- Ivanov, S., Vasilev, V. 1975. Studies of the animal bone material of the prehistoric settlement mound near Golyamo Delchevo. In: Todorova, H., Ivanov, St., Vasilev, V., Hopff, M., Kwitta, H., Koll, G. (Eds), *Settlement Mound Near Golyamo Delchevo. Razkopki i prouchvaniya* 5, 245–302 (in Bulgarian).
- Ivanov, S., Vasilev, V. 1979. Examination of animal bone remains. In: Georgiev, G., Merpert, N., Katincharov, R., Dimitrov, D. (Eds), *Ezero – the settlement of the Early Bronze Age*. Bulgarian Academy of Sciences Academic Press, Sofia, 425–490 (in Bulgarian).
- Ivanov, S. 1959a. Les animaux sauvage et domestiques dans la vie quotidienne de la population de Yassa-Tepe à Plovdiv. *Annuaire de Musée archéologique populaire – Plovdiv* 11, 81–86.
- Ivanov, S. 1959b. Die Fleischnahrung der Bewohner am südlichen Stadttor von Preslav. *Bulletin de l’Institut archeologique* 22, 209–221 (in Bulgarian, with German abstract).
- Ivanov, S. 1965. Animal bone remains of the settlement in the Dzhezdhovi Lozya Locality near Popina village. In: Vazharova, Z. (Ed.), *Slavic and Slavic-Bulgarian Settlements in the Bulgarian Lands of the End of the 6th–11th centuries*. Bulgarian Academy of Sciences Academic Press, Sofia, 207–221 (in Bulgarian).
- Ivanov, S., Vasilev, V. 1979. Investigations of the animal bone remains. In: Georgiev G., Merpert, N., Katincharov R., Dimitrov D. (Eds), *Ezero – the Early Bronze Age Settlement*. Bulgarian Academy of Sciences Academic Press, Sofia, 425–490 (in Bulgarian).
- Ivanov, T., Slokoska, L., Georgiev, P., Ivanov, R., Kabakchieva, G., Vacheva, M., Nacheva, V., Goshev, S., Tsarov, I., Vladkova, P., Valkov, I., Poulter, A., Streinch, P., Dowsen, M., Sheppard, D., Beech, M., Cenneth, D., Lutton, A. 1987. Excavations in Nicopolis-ad-Istrum (Bulgarian-English Expedition). In: Velkov, V. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1986*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Razgrad, 121–127 (in Bulgarian).
- Ivanova, S. 1995. Drilling studies in Magurata Cave, Rabisha village. Quaternary stratigraphy. *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1994*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Sliven, 11–13 (in Bulgarian).
- Ivanova, S., Gurova, M., Spassov, N., Hristova, L., Tzankov, N., Popov, V., Marinova, E., Makedonska, J., Smith, V., Ottoni, C., Lewis, M. 2016. Magura Cave, Bulgaria: A multidisciplinary study of Late Pleistocene human palaeoenvironment in the Balkans. *Quaternary International* 415, 86–108, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2015.11.082>.
- Ivanova, S., Gurova, M., Spassov, N., Popov, V., Makedonska, J., Tzankov, T., Strait, D. 2012. Preliminary Findings of the Balkan Paleo Project: Evidence of Human Activity at the “Gateway” of Europe during the Late Pleistocene. *Bulgarian e-Journal of Archaeology* 2(2), 2–23, <https://be-ja.org/index.php/journal/issue/view/be-ja-2-2-2012/be-ja-2-2-2012>.
- Ivanova, S., Gurova, M., Spassov, N., Popov, V. 2011. Sound-ing archaeological studies in the Leyarnite cave complex,

- Mladezhko village, Malko Tarnovo Municipality. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological discoveries and excavations in 2010*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Sofia, 31–34.
- Ivanova, S., Gurova, M., Spassov, N. 2012. Study of the Pleistocene sediments in the Magurata Cave. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2011*. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 32–34.
- Ivanova, S., Gurova, M., Spassov, N., Popov, V. 2011. Drilling archaeological researches in the Leyarnite cave complex, Mladezhko village, Malko Tarnovo Municipality. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2010*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 31–34 (in Bulgarian).
- Ivanova, S., Gyurova, M., Datsov, S., Straight, D. 2014. Archaeological study of the Belimel Cave, Chiprovtsi region. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1983*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. TDG Print, Sofia, 34–35 (in Bulgarian).
- Ivanova, S., Gyurova, M., Spasov, N., Christ, L., Gyaurova, B., Makedonska, Z., Anastasova, E., Marinova, E., Hodgkins, J., Miller, C., Straight, D. 2013. Archaeological excavations in Magura Cave. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2012*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Kolbis Publishing House, Sofia, 34–37 (in Bulgarian).
- Ivanova, S., Krumov, I., Spasov, N., Hristova, L., Makedonska, J., Gyurova, M., Straight, D. 2019. Excavations in the Mishin Kamik Cave, near Chiprovtsi. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1983*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. TDG Print, Sofia, 31–34 (in Bulgarian).
- Ivanova, S., Krumov, I., Spasov, N., Hristova, L., Makedonska, J., Gurova, M., Strait, D., 2014. Excavations in the Misin Kamak Cave, Ciprovci. In: Gurova M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2013*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. TDG Print, Sofia, 31–35 (in Bulgarian).
- Ivanova, S., Spassov, N., Boyadzhiev, K. 2012. Prehistoric rock structure in the Harman Kaya locality, Gasak neighbourhood, Bivoljane village. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2011*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 85–87 (in Bulgarian).
- Iwanoff, S. 1949. Über einen fund von *Bos primigenius* Bojan aus der spathistorischen zeit in Bulgarien. *Annuaire de l'Académie Rurale "G. Dimitroff" – Sofia, Faculté de médecine vétérinaire* 26, 335–338.
- Kalchev, P., Andreeva, D. 2017. Rescue archeological excavations at a prehistoric site near the village of Madzherito, Stara Zagora municipality. In: Vagalinski, L. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2016*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Bulged, Sofia, 437–441 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Kancheva-Ruseva, T., Ignatov, V., Velkov, K., Rusev, S. 2008. *Archeological and Historical Research in the Region of Nova Zagora, Vol. 2*. Agato Publishers, Sofia, 298 pp. (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Kancheva-Ruseva, T., Koleva, D. 2011. Archaeological surveys of the site 18, am Thracia, lot 2, km 236 + 850-237 + 060, Yurta Locality, Zagortsi village, Nova Zagora Municipality. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2010*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 147–150 (in Bulgarian).
- Karastoyanova, N. 2011. *Animals in ritual context: Archeozoological study of excavated structure from the Late Neolithic ritual complex near Sarnevo, Stara Zagora*. Master's thesis, Department of Archeology, New Bulgarian University, Sofia, 151 pp. (in Bulgarian).
- Karastoyanova, N. 2018. *Development of hunting and husbandry and changes in natural environment from the Late Neolithic to the Late Chalcolithic period in Eastern Bulgaria according to data from archaeological sites*. PhD thesis, National Museum of Natural History, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia, 221 pp. (in Bulgarian).
- Karastoyanova, N., Chohadziev, A. 2019. Hunting and stockbreeding in the early Chalcolithic: osteological analysis of mammalian remains in Petko Karavelovo tell, Veliko Tarnovo region. *Annual of the Department of Natural Sciences, New Bulgarian University* 5, 96–108.
- Karastoyanova, N., Gorczyk, J., Spassov, N. 2019. The natural history of the fallow deer, *Dama dama* (Linnaeus, 1758) in Bulgaria in prehistory and new evidence for the existence of an autochthonous Holocene population in the Balkans. *International Journal of Osteoarchaeology* 30 (5), 616–628, <https://doi.org/10.1002/oa.2886>.
- Katincharov, R., Kanchev, M. 1977. Excavations of the settlement mound in the town of Nova Zagora. In: Velkov, V., Katincharov, R. (Eds), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1976. Proceedings of the 22nd National Archeological Conference*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Regional Historical Museum, Ruse, 30–31 (in Bulgarian).
- Kisyov, K. 1987. Excavation of a Thracian mound necropolis in the land of the Borino village, Smolyan Region. In: Velkov, V. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1986*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Razgrad, 107–109 (in Bulgarian).
- Kitov, G., Borisova, T. 1988. Detours and excavations of Thracian mounds in the Pravets Municipality. In: Velkov, V. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1987*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Blagoevgrad, p. 63 (in Bulgarian).
- Kitov, G., Borisova, T. 1994. Mound necropolis near Kalugerovo village, Pravets region in 1993. In: Velkov, V., Katincharov, R. (Eds), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1992–1993*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Veliko Tarnovo, 41–42 (in Bulgarian).
- Klasnakov, M., Leshtakov, P., Samichkova, G., Alexandrova, R., Spasov, N., Iliev, N., Zlateva, R. 2011. Rescue archaeological study of the Late Neolithic village of Budzhaka in the area of UPI 8035, town of Sozopol, Burgas District. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2010*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 25–28 (in Bulgarian).
- Klasnakov, M., Samichkova, G., Gyurova, M. 2010. Drilling Excavations of Burgas Village Municipality. In: Gergova, D. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2009*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 61–64 (in Bulgarian).
- Kodzhabashev, N.D., Tsvyatkova, D.D., Krastev, K.V., Ignatov, M.M., Teofilova, T.M. 2021. The Eurasian Beaver *Castor fiber* Linnaeus, 1758 (Rodentia: Castoridae) is Returning to Bulgaria. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 73 (4), 587–595.
- Komitov, E. 2016. The Wisent (*Bison bonasus* L.) in Bulgaria. *Forest Science* 1–2, 117–128 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).

- Kovachev, G., Minkov, T. 1986. Wild animals of the prehistoric settlement near Rakitovo. *Annual of Sofia University "Kliment Ohridski", Faculty of Biology* 77 (1) 87–100 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Kovachev, G. 1988. *Wild and domestic animals of the Neolithic settlements near Kazanlak, Rakitovo and Kalugerovo – osteoscopic and osteometric research*. DSc thesis abstract, Higher Institute of Zootechnics and Veterinary Medicine, Stara Zagora, 1–36 (in Bulgarian).
- Kuzov, H., Hristov, M., Rusev, N. 2017. Archaeological studies of the late Antique settlement Timum. In: Vagalinski, L. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2016*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Bulged, Sofia, 402–404 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Lazarov, M., Porozhanov, K., Popov, V. 1988. Urdoviza. In: Velkov, V. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1987*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Blagoevgrad, 39–40 (in Bulgarian).
- Leshtakov, K., Todorova, N., Petrova, V., Zlatem-Uzunova, R., Ozbek, O., Popova, T., Spassov, N., Iliev, N. 2007. Preliminary report on the salvage archaeological excavations at the Early Neolithic site Yabalkovo in the Maritsa Valley, 2000–2005 field seasons. *Anatolica* 33, 185–234, <https://doi.org/10.2143/ANA.33.0.2021759>.
- Manhart, H. 1998. Die vorgeschichtliche Tierwelt von Koprivec und Durankulak und anderen prähistorischen Fundplätzen in Bulgarien aufgrund von Knochenfunden aus archäologischen Ausgrabungen. *Documenta naturae* 116, 1–353.
- Manova, E. Asparuhov, M. 1983. Excavations of the medieval fortress near Nikopol. In: Velkov, V. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1982*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Pleven, 131–132 (in Bulgarian).
- Markov, G. 1951. Les mamifères quaternaires en Bulgarie. *Bulletin de l'Institut zoologique de l'Académie bulgare des Sciences* 1, 99–199 (in Bulgarian, with French abstract).
- Markov, G. 1958. Beiträge zur geschichte der säugetiere in Bulgarien (Material aus Seuthopolis). *Bulletin de l'Institut zoologique de l'Académie bulgare des Sciences* 7, 133–161 (in Bulgarian, with German abstract).
- Markov, G. 1963. Beiträge zur untersuchung des höhlenbären (*Ursus spelaeus* Blumenb.) in Bulgarien. *Bulletin de l'Institut de Zoologie et Musée* 14, 5–26.
- Markov, G. 2004. The fossil proboscideans of Bulgaria and the importance of some Bulgarian finds – a brief review. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 16, 139–150.
- Markov, G., Petrov, P. 1962. The red reer (*Cervus elaphus*) in Bulgaria. *Priroda* 2, 19–25.
- Melamed, K., Evtimova, E. 2018. Rescue archaeological excavations in the National Academy of Arts – eastern courtyard, Sofia. In: Vagalinski, L. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2017*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Bulged, Sofia, 557–559 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Mikov, V., Dzhambazov, V. 1960. *The Devetashkata Cave*. Bulgarian Academy of Sciences Academic Press, Sofia, 200 pp.
- Mikov, V. 1926. Caves and precipices between the Iskar and Vit rivers. *Estestvoznanie i geographiya* 7–8, 236–249 (in Bulgarian).
- Mikov, V. 1927a. Le tumulus préhistorique de Balbounar. *Bulletin de l'Institut archeologique bulgare* 6, 251–284 (in Bulgarian, with French abstract).
- Mikov, V. 1927b. The Devetaska Cave and Lazhenska Cave. *Balgarski turist* 5, 73–75 (in Bulgarian).
- Mikov, V. 1928. Caves in the Belogradchik Region. *Balgarski turist* 3, 43–44 (in Bulgarian).
- Mikov, V. 1936. Investigations of the traces of the primitive man in our caves. *Izvestiya na balgarskoto peshterno druzhestvo* 1, 42–49 (in Bulgarian).
- Mikov, V. 1933. The pre-Thracian population of our lands. Festschrift Anastas T. Ischirkov zu seiner 35-jährigen akademischen lehrtätigkeit gewidmet. *Mitteilungen der Bulgarischen Geographischen Gesellschaft* 1, 233–244 (in Bulgarian).
- Milchev, B., Boev, Z. 2014. First record of the Naumann's Thrush (*Turdus naumanni* Temminck, 1820 s. l.) in Bulgaria. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 66 (4), 559–561.
- Miltschew, B., Georgiewa, U. 1998. Erstbeobachtung des Alpenschneehuhns *Lagopus mutus* in Bulgarien. *Ornithologische Mitteilungen* 50 (2), 43–44.
- Mitev, I. 2004. New data on the Holocene distribution of the Southern Birch Mouse (*Sicista subtilis* (Pallas, 1773)) in Bulgaria. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 16, 133–138.
- Mitev, I. 2005. New data on the Holocene Distribution of the Common Hamster (*Cricetus cricetus* L., 1758) in Bulgaria. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 57 (1), 113–121.
- Mitev, I. 2006. Subfossil finds of birds and mammals in accumulations of the food of Eagle Owl (*Bubo bubo* (L., 1758)) (Aves: Strigiformes) from the valley of Rusenski Lom River. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 17, 137–151.
- Mitev, I. 2016. Subfossil materials of birds and mammals from a site of the Tawny Owl (*Strix aluco* L.) near Pisanets village (Ruse Region). In: Boev, Z. (Ed.), *Ivan Mitev. Selected Works, Vol. 1. Bulgarian Nature*. Logis Publishing House, Sofia, 859–888.
- Mitev, I. 2016a. Comparative analysis of the food spectrum of the Eagle owl (*Bubo bubo* (Linnaeus, 1758)) in two localities from the Northeast Bulgaria. In: Boev, Z. (Ed.), *Ivan Mitev. Selected Works, Vol. 1. Bulgarian Nature*. Logis Publishing House, Sofia, 118–154.
- Mitev, I. 2016b. Holocene fauna of birds and mammals of Northeastern Bulgaria (according data until 1996). In: Boev, Z. (Ed.), *Ivan Mitev. Selected Works, Vol. 1. Bulgarian Nature*. Logis Publishing House, Sofia, 180–193.
- Mitev, I. 2016c. Subfossil birds and mammals from two localities along the Danube River (Ruse Region, NE Bulgaria). In: Boev, Z. (Ed.), *Ivan Mitev. Selected Works, Vol. 1. Bulgarian Nature*. Logis Publishing House, Sofia, 844–858.
- Mitev, I. 2016d. Subfossil fauna of birds and mammals (Aves et Mammalia – Vertebrata) of localitis of Northeastern Bulgaria. In: Boev, Z. (Ed.), *Ivan Mitev. Selected Works, Vol. 1. Bulgarian Nature*. Logis Publishing House, Sofia, 203–691.
- Mitev, I., Boev, Z. 2006. Food spectrum of the Eagle Owl (*Bubo bubo* (L., 1758)) (Aves: Strigiformes) from two Holocene localities in NE Bulgaria. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 17, 153–165 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Miteva, V. 2008. Predators as a factor in the accumulation and transformation of bones in archaeological context: An example from the Late Palaeolithic assemblage from the Kozarnika cave, Northern Bulgaria. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Prehistoric Research in Bulgaria: New Challenges. Proceedings of the National Prehistory Conference, Peshtera*, 15–23.
- Mlynarski, M. 1982. Amphibia and Reptilia. In: Kowalski, K. (Ed.), *Excavation in the Bacho Kiro Cave (Bulgaria). Final Report*. Państwowe Wydawnictwo Naukowe, Warszawa, 29–31.
- Moreva-Arabova, R., Dukov, I., Krasteva, Z. 2012. Archaeological excavations of Assen's Fortress. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2011*. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 461–464 (in Bulgarian).

- Nakamura, H. 2005. The Preliminary Analysis of the Animal Bones Found in Dyadovo tell. In: Kamuro, H. (Ed.), *Dyadovo Excavation 2004. A Preliminary Report of the 16th Excavation at Dyadovo, Bulgaria*. Tokai University Thracian Expedition. Grant-in-Aid for Scientific Research (B), 2004, No 16401019. *Dyadovo Studies* 4, 24–25.
- Nehrizov, G., Ivanov, G. 2011. A settlement of the early Bronze Age near Sedlari village, Gradinka Neighbourhood, Momchilgrad Municipality. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2010*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 110–113 (in Bulgarian).
- Nehrizov, G., Tsvetkova, Y. 2012. Gluhite Kamani Rock complex. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2011*. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 127–130 (in Bulgarian).
- Neov, B., Spassov, N., Hristova, L., Hristov, P., Radoslavov, G. 2021. New data on the evolutionary history of the European bison (*Bison bonasus*) based on subfossil remains from Southeastern Europe. *Ecology and Evolution* 11 (6), 2842–2848, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.7241>.
- Nikolov, I. 1977b. Review of the cave fossil mammalian fauna in Bulgaria and further problems. In: Dinev, L., Panayotov, T., Popov, V. (Eds.), *Speleology. Reports of the Speleological Conference*, Sofia, 93–101 (in Bulgarian).
- Nikolov, I. 1983. Some notes on the cave fossil mammalian fauna in Bulgaria. In: Dinev, L. (Chief Ed.), *4th European Regional Conference of Speleology*, Sofia, 215–218 (in Bulgarian).
- Ninov, L. 1987. Archeozoological studies of the prehistoric settlement Slatino, Kyustendil Region. In: Velkov, V. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1986*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Razgrad, 44–47 (in Bulgarian).
- Ninov, L. 1989. Osteological studies in 1988. In: Velkov, V. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1988. Proceedings of the 34th National Conference of Archaeology*, Kardzhali, 169–171 (in Bulgarian).
- Ninov, L. 1991. Animal bones of early complexes in the region of Pliska. *Problems of the Protobulgarian History and Culture, Vol. 2*. Bulgarian Academy of Sciences Academic Press, Sofia, 239–246 (in Bulgarian).
- Ninov, L. 1994a. Study of the animal remains of prehistoric sites. In: Velkov, V., Katincharov, R. (Eds.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1992–1993*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Veliko Tarnovo, 26–27 (in Bulgarian).
- Ninov, L. 1994b. Osteological studies of antique sites. In: Velkov, V., Katincharov, R. (Eds.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1992–1993*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Veliko Tarnovo, 94–95 (in Bulgarian).
- Ninov, L. 1995. Osteoarcheological researches of prehistoric sites. *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1994*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Sliven, p. 37 (in Bulgarian).
- Ninov, L. 2010. Remains of the fauna in the prehistoric sites. In: Gergova, D. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2009*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 105–107 (in Bulgarian).
- Ninov, L. 2012a. Osteological studies of objects from the Bronze and Iron Ages. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2011*. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 219–221 (in Bulgarian).
- Ninov, L. 2012b. Osteological studies of ancient objects. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2011*. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 369–371 (in Bulgarian).
- Ninov, L. 2012c. Archeozoological studies of medieval fortresses and tombs. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2011*. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 504–506 (in Bulgarian).
- Ninov, L. 2012d. Archeozoological studies of prehistoric settlements and necropolis in 2011. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2011*. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 601–604 (in Bulgarian).
- Ninov, L. 2013a. Archaeozoological studies of prehistoric sites. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2012*. BAS, National Archeological Institute with Museum. Kolbis Publishing House, Sofia, 90–92 (in Bulgarian).
- Ninov, L. 2013b. Archeosteological studies of antique sites. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2012*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Kolbis Publishing House, Sofia, 346–346 (in Bulgarian).
- Ninov, L. 2013c. Archeozoological studies of Medieval sites. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2012*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Kolbis Publishing House, Sofia, 505–506 (in Bulgarian).
- Ninov, L. 2014. Archeosteological studies of antique sites. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1983*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. TDG Print, Sofia, 429–431 (in Bulgarian).
- Ninov, L. 2016. Archeozoological research of settlements, cult sites and other contexts, studied in 2015. In: Aladzhov, A. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2015*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Multiprint, Sofia, 966–967 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Nobis, G. 2002a. Zur Fauna der prähistorischen Siedlung Durankulak, Bez. Tolbuchin (NO-Bulgarien) I. Das Neolithikum. In: Nobis, G. (Ed.), *Die Tierwelt Nordost-Bulgariens vom Neolithikum um bis zur Kupferzeit anhand archäologischer grabungen in Durankulak (Bez. Tolbuchin), Podgorica und vom tell Targoviste*. Bonner Zoologische Monographien 51, 11–27.
- Nobis, G. 2002b. Studien an mittel- bis spatneolithischen Tierresten von Podgorica (NO-Bulgarien). In: Nobis, G. (Ed.), *Die Tierwelt Nordost-Bulgariens vom Neolithikum um bis zur Kupferzeit anhand archäologischer grabungen in Durankulak (Bez. Tolbuchin), Podgorica und vom tell Targoviste*. Bonner Zoologische Monographien 51, 63–86.
- Nobis, G., Ninov, L. 2002. Zur Fauna der prähistorischen Siedlung Durankulak, Bez. Tolbuchin (NO-Bulgarien). II. Die Kupferzeit. In: Nobis, G. (Ed.), *Die Tierwelt Nordost-Bulgariens vom Neolithikum um bis zur Kupferzeit anhand archäologischer grabungen in Durankulak (Bez. Tolbuchin), Podgorica und vom tell Targoviste*. Bonner Zoologische Monographien 51, 29–59.
- Peshev, T., Peshev, D., Popov, V. 2004. *Fauna of Bulgaria. Vol. 27 Mammalia*. Prof. Marin Drinov Academic Press, Sofia, 632 pp. (in Bulgarian, with English summary).
- Petkov, P. 1930. Current and former wisents. *Lovets* 10, 154–157 (in Bulgarian).
- Petkov, P. 1931. Primitive wild cattle in Bulgaria. *Lovets* 31 (5), 71–73 (in Bulgarian).
- Petkov, P. 1934. Neolithic remains of *Bos primigenius* Bojan in Bulgaria. *Annuaire de l'Université de Sofia, Faculté d'agronomie* 12 (in Bulgarian).

- Petrov, A. 1964. Wild and domestic cattle of Deluvial epoch of the Central Europe and our lands. *Zhivotnovadni nauki* 1 (1), 25–38 (in Bulgarian).
- Petrov, A. 1964. Wild cattle of the Deluvial epoch of the Middle Europe and our lands. *Zhivotnovadni nauki* 1 (1), 25–38 (in Bulgarian).
- Petrov, I. 1988. Thracian burial mound near Gorski Izvor village, Haskovo Region. In: Velkov, V. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1987*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Blagoevgrad, 65–66 (in Bulgarian).
- Petrunova, B., Petrunov, P., Kiryakova, V. 2019. Archaeological excavations at the Liutitsa fortress. In: Popov, H. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2018*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Bulged, Sofia, 533–535 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Plachiyiski, D., Popgeorgiev G., Avramov S., Boev, Z. 2018. The Balkan capercaillie *Tetrao urogallus rudolfi* Dombrowski, 1912 (Galliformes: Phasianidae): Distribution, history and current status in Bulgaria. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 70 (1), 101–111.
- Popoff, R. 1920. Beitrag zur Erforschung der Jagd, der Landwirtschaft, der Viehzucht und der Fischerei in der prahisforschenden und der Frühhisforischen Zeit. *Spisanie na zemedelskite izpitatelni instituti v Balgariya* 1, 1–21 (in Bulgarian, with German abstract).
- Popov, R. 1904. A contribution to the prehistory of Bulgaria (the caves of the Tarnovo Derwent, the settlement of Madara and the caves above Sumen. *Sbornik za narodni umotvorenia* 20, 1–27 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1908. A contribution to the Neolithic mammalian fauna in Bulgaria. *Sbornik za narodni umotvoreniya, Nauka i knizhnina* 22, 1–22 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1908. A contribution to the prehistory of Bulgaria. *Sbornik za narodni umotvorenia* 24, 1–18 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1909. Kodzha-Dermenska mound. A contribution to the prehistory of Bulgaria. *Periodichesko spisanie* 21, 502–562 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1911. Malkata Cave in the Tarnovo Derwent. *Estestvoznanie* 3, 148–166 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1912. Excavations of the Malkata Cave neat Tarnovo in 1901. *Bulletin of the Bulgarian Archeological Society* 2, 248–256 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1912. Matériaux de la station “Pod-gradá” près du village Madara, ar. de Choumen. *Izvestiya na balgarskoto arheologichesko druzhestvo* 3, 90–107 (in Bulgarian, with French abstract).
- Popov, R. 1913. Beitrag zur Kenntnis der Diluvial fauna Bulgariens. *Spisanie na Balgarskata Akademiya na naukite* 7, 115–142 (in Bulgarian, with German abstract).
- Popov, R. 1913. *Fouilles de la grotte “Morovitsa”*. Imprimerie de la Cour Royale, Sophia, 263–290 (in Bulgarian, with French abstract).
- Popov, R. 1914. Malka Cave. *Balgarski turist* 4, 57–60.
- Popov, R. 1920. Morovitsa Cave. *Estestvoznanie i geografija* 9–10, 424–440 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1920. The prehistoric man of the Paleolithic epoch. *Estestvoznanie i geografija* 1 (2), 1–40 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1921. Tsar’s Cave. *Estestvoznanie i geografija* 6, 28–33 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1921. The Golyama Lisitsa Cave. *Estestvoznanie i geografija* 2–3, 95–105 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1923. The bave bear (*Ursus spelaeus* Blumb). *Estestvoznanie i geografija* 6, 176–180 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1924. Remains of beaver in Bulgaria. *Estvoznanie i geografija* 4–5, 144–146 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1925. The Belyakovsko plateau. Caves and prehistoric settlements. *Izdaniya na Narodniya muzey v Sofia* 3, 1–58 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1925b. New findings of the prehistoric man in Bulgaria. *Priroda* 3–4, 33–34 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1926. The Temnata Doupka Cave near Karlukovo. *Balgarski turist* 1, 5–8 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1928. *Culture and Life of the Prehistoric Man in Bulgaria. Part I. Stone Epoch*. Bulgarian Archeological Institute, Sofia, 64 pp. (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1929. *Prehistorical Bulgaria*. Hristo Danov Publishing House, Sofia, 76 pp. (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1929. *The Man of the Ice Epoch in Europe*. Hudozhnik Printing House, Sofia, 1–80 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1931. *Temnata Dupka – a new locality of the Paleolithic in Bulgaria*. *Izdaniya na Narodniya arheologicheski muzey v Sofia*. State Printing House, Sofia, 148 pp. (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1933. Materials for studying of subfossil species of the genus *Felis*. *Mitteilungen der Bulgarischen Geographischen Gesellschaft* 1, 293–298 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1933. The Mirizlivka Cave. A contribution to the deluvial fauna and the culture of the deluvial man. *Izdaniya na Narodniya arheologicheski muzey* 26, 1–74 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1933b. Materials for studying of subfossil species of the genus *Felis*. *Mitteilungen der Bulgarischen Geographischen Gesellschaft* 1, 293–298 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1934. Materials on the prehistory of Madara. In: Madara excavations and studies 1, 15–64 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1934a. Fossilized remains of the ibex (*Capra aegagrus*) found in Bulgaria. *Priroda i nauka* 8–9, 128–129 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1934b. *Animals Bones of Historical Time. Madara. Excavations and Researches, Book 1*. *Izdaniya na Narodniya arheologicheski muzey*. State Printing House, Sofia, 221–239 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1936a. Fossil and subfossil animal remains in the explored until now caves in Bulgaria. *Bulletin de la Société Spéléologique de Sofia* 1, 1–12 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1936b. Trouvailles des fouilles de Madara – campagnes de 1934 et de 1935. *Editions du Musée National Bulgare* 33, 31–98 (in Bulgarian, with French abstract).
- Popov, R. 1936c. Investigations on the dog breed from tomb No II at Madara. *Editions du Museum National Bulgare* 33, 99–105 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1937. Excavations in the Golyama Peshtera Cave near Dryanovski Monastery. *Priroda i nauka* 1, 8–9 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1938. Oldest human remains in Bulgaria. *Rodina* 1, 66–117 (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, R. 1943. *Short Handbook of Prehistory, Part. 1. Paleolithic (Old Stone Age in regards of the Paleolithic in Bulgaria)*. University Printing House, Sofia, 154 pp. (in Bulgarian).
- Popov, V., Lakovski, K. 2019. Southernmost Postglacial Record of Pond Bat *Myotis dasycneme* (Boie, 1825) (Mammalia: Chiroptera) – Varteshka Cave, NW Bulgaria. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 71 (1), 57–62.
- Popov, V., Marinska, M. 2007. An almost one million year long (Early to Late Pleistocene) small mammal succession from the archaeological layers of Kozarnika Cave in Northern Bulgaria. *Courier Forschungsinstitut Senckenberg* 259, 79–92.
- Popov, V. 1990. *Quaternary small mammals (Mammalia: Insectivora, Lagomorpha, Rodentia) of the Western Pre-*

- Balkan: morphology, palaeoecology, biostratigraphy*. PhD thesis, Institute of Zoology, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia, 215 pp.
- Popov, V. 1994. Quaternary small mammals from deposits in Temnata-Prohodna Cave system. In: Ginter, B., Kozłowski, J., Laville, H. (Eds), *Temnata Cave. Excavations in Karlukovo Karst Area, Bulgaria, Vol. 1, Part 2*. Jagellonian University Press, Krakow, 11–53.
- Popov, V. 2017. Early Pleistocene small mammals (Eulipotyphla, Chiroptera, Lagomorpha and Rodentia) from Futjova Cave, North Bulgaria. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 69 (2), 263–282.
- Popov, V. 2018. Chapter 3. Pliocene–Quaternary small mammals (Eulipotyphla, Chiroptera, Lagomorpha, Rodentia) in Bulgaria: Biostratigraphy, paleoecology, and evolution. In: Huard, G., Gareau, J. (Eds), *The Pleistocene*. Nova Science Publishers Inc., New York, 1–134.
- Popov, V., Gerasimov, S., Marinska, M. 1994. Multivariate palaeoecological analysis of a Late Quaternary small mammal succession from North Bulgaria. *Historical Biology* 8 (1–4), 261–274. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10292389409380480>.
- Poppow, R. 1913. Die Ausgrabungen in der Höhle “Malkata Podlisza” bei den Dorfe Beljakovez, unweit der Stadt Tirnovo (Nordbulgarien). *Prähistorischen Zeitschrift* 5 (3–4), 449–460.
- Rabadjiev, K., Valchev, I., Handzhiyska, V., Lozanov, I., Kolev, P., Krumova, M., Tonkova, E., Kozarev, M. 2018. Archeological reserve “ancient Thracian town Cabyle”. Excavations in sector 5. In: Vagalinski, L. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2017*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Bulged, Sofia, 300–303 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Raduncheva, A., Koleva, B. 1992. Excavations of the Chelcolithic Cult Centre near the Dolnoslav village, Plovdiv Region. *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1991*. Ministry of Culture, Sofia, 22–23 (in Bulgarian).
- Rashev, R., Stanilov, S., Atanasov, G. 1988. Early medieval necropolis near Nozharevo village, Razgrad Region. In: Velkov, V. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1987*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Blagoevgrad, p. 206 (in Bulgarian).
- Ribarov, G., Boev, Z. 1997. Bone remains of wild and domestic animals from the Telish-Redoutite prehistoric settlement near Telish (Pleven district). *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 7, 61–70 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Ribarov, G. 1982. Donnees nouvelles pour la faune de la ville antique Kabile. *Bulletin des musées de la Bulgarie du Sud-Est* 6, 31–41 (in Bulgarian, with French abstract).
- Ribarov, G. 1983. The fallow deer in our lands. *Priroda* 2, 58–59 (in Bulgarian).
- Ribarov, G. 1986. Impoverishment of the mammal fauna in the surroundings of Kabile (I millennium BC – VI century AD). *Settlement Life in Thrace. Second Symposium*, Yambol, 177–185 (in Bulgarian).
- Ribarov, G. 1990. Les mammifères dans la vie des habitants de la haute époque byzantine et du Moyen âge du Hissarlik (Sliven). *Arheologiya* 4, 50–58 (in Bulgarian, with French abstract).
- Ribarov, G. 1991a. Archeozoological material from the Eneolithic and Early Bronze Age Settlement at Sozopol. In: Lazarov, M., Angelova, H. (Eds), *Proceedings of the International Symposium Thracia Pontica* 5, 1–57.
- Ribarov, G. 1991b. La faune de Cabyle (I-ère millénaire av. n. ère – VI s. de n. ère) d’après les restes d’animaux sauvages et domestiques. In: Velkov V. (Ed.), *Kabile, Vol. 2*. Bulgarian Academy of Sciences Academic Press, Sofia, 156–167 (in Bulgarian, with Russian and French summaries).
- Ribarov, G. 1991c. The osteological material from the sunken settlement at Ourdoviza. In: Lazarov, M., Angelova, H. (Eds), *Proceedings of the International Symposium Thracia Pontica* 5, 113–118.
- Ribarov, G. 1992a. Study of the Neolithic animal remains from the settlement near thevillage Maluk Preslavets, District Silistra. *Dobrudzha* 9, 85–90 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Ribarov, G. 1992b. Les chameaux de la region Sud-Est européenne pendant L’antiquité et le moyen age. *Bulletin des musées de la Bulgarie du Sud-Est* 16, 401–409.
- Ribarov, G. 1994. Fishing traditions of inhabitants of ancient Cabyle and its hinterland. *Proceedings of the 3rd International Symposium Cabyle*, 421–425.
- Ribarov, G. 2021. Domestic and wild animals of the medieval fortress Rusokastro, Burgas Region. *Bulletin of the Burgas Museum* 7, 290–311 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Ribarov, G., Boev, Z. 1990. Investigation of the animal remains from the Late Iron Age Yassa-Tepe near Yambol. *Interdisciplinarni izsledvaniya, National Institute of Archeology and Museum* 17, 83–90 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Roberts, N. 2009. Holocene climates. In: Gornitz, V. (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of Paleoclimatology and Ancient Environments*. Springer, New York, 438–442. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-4411-3_106.
- Schramm, Z. 1975. Zwierzęce szczątki kostne. In: Parnicki-Pudelko, S. (Ed.), *Novae – Sektor Zachodni 1972*. Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznań, 215–241.
- Schramm, Z. 1979. Zwierzęce szczątki kostne. In: Parnicki-Pudelko, S. (Ed.), *Novae – Sektor Zachodni 1978–1979*. Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznań, 97–130.
- Schranke, H., Wolf, A. 1938. Beiträge zur Kenntniss der Vogelwelt Bulgarisch-Macedoniens. *Journal für Ornithologie* 86, 309–327. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01947430>.
- Sirakov, N. 1984. Archaeological and paleoecological research of the karst area in the vicinity of Lukovit and Karlukovo, Lovech District. In: Velkov, V. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1983*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Smolyan, 6–8.
- Sirakov, N., Guadeli, J.-L., Sirakova, S., Ferrier, C., Fernandez, P., Taneva, S., Miteva, V., Guadeli, A., Dimitrova, I., Spasov, R. 2013. Kozarnika: a cave dwelling of the Paleolithic in the Belogradchik Karst. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2012*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Kolbis Publishing House, Sofia, 27–29 (in Bulgarian).
- Sirakov, N., Guadeli, J.-L., Sirakova, S., Ivanova, S., Fernandez, F., Taneva, S., Guadeli, A., Miteva, V., Krumov, I., Dimitrova, I., Spasov, R. 2012. Bulgarian-French studies of Paleolithic residences in the Kozarnika Cave. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2011*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 27–29 (in Bulgarian).
- Sirakov, N., Guadeli, J.-L., Sirakova, S., Ivanova, S., Popov, V., Fernandez, P., Ferrier, C., LeBlanc, J.-C., Taneva, S., Dimitrova, I. 2010. Paleolithic surveys in the Kozarnika Cave, Belfgradchik Region in 2009. In: Gergova, D. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2009*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 23–26 (in Bulgarian).
- Sirakov, N., Guadeli, J.-L., Ivanova, S., Sirakova, S., Boudadi-Maligne, M., Dimitrova, I., Fernandez, P., Ferrier, C., Gua-

- delli, A., Iordanova, D., Iordanova, N., Kovatcheva, M., Krumov, I., Leblanc, J.-C., Miteva, V., Popov, V., Spassov, R., Taneva, S., Tsanova, T. 2010. An ancient continuous human presence in the Balkans and the beginnings of human settlement in western Eurasia: A Early Pleistocene example of the Early Palaeolithic levels in Kozarnika Cave (Northwestern Bulgaria). *Quaternary International* 223–224, 94–106, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2010.02.023>.
- Sirakov, N., Guadelli, J.-L., Sirakova, S., Guadelli, A., Taneva, S., Krumov, I., Dimitrova, I., Zahariev, N. 2019a. The Paleolithic cave site of Kozarnika: transition from middle to Late Paleolithic. *In: Popov, H. (Ed.), Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2018*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Bulged, Sofia, 1–3 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Sirakov, N., Guadelli, J.-L., Sirakova, S., Guadelli, A., Taneva, S., Krumov, I., Hopkins, R., Dimitrova, I., Zahariev, N., Dimitrov, T. 2018. Kozarnika: the first possible predecessors of the Late Paleolithic precede significantly the end of the middle Paleolithic. *In: Vagalinski, L. (Ed.), Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2017*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Bulged, Sofia, 1–4 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Sirakov, N., Guadelli, J.-L., Sirakova, S., Taneva, S., Guadelli, A., Miteva, V., Krumov, I., Dimitrova, I., Zahariev, N., Nikolov, P. 2016b. Kozarnika: First occupation of the modern man in the early Late Paleolithic. *In: Aladzhov, A. (Ed.), Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2015*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Multiprint, Bulgaria, 43–46 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Sirakov, N., Tsanova, T., Hublin, J.-J., Sirakova, S., McPherron, S., Talamo, S., Marreiros, J., Smith, G., Fewllas, H., Krumov, I., Spassov, R., Rezek, Z., Sinet-Mathiot, V., Zahariev, N. 2017. Reopened Bacho Kiro Cave: new data on the middle/Late Palaeolithic transition and early-middle stages of the Late Palaeolithic. *In: Vagalinski, L. (Ed.), Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2016*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Bulged, Sofia, 44–47 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Sirakov, N., Tsanova, T., Hublin, J.-J., Sirakova, S., McPherron, S., Krumov, I., Spasov, R., Zahariev, N., Anasstassova, E., Fewllas, H. 2019b. The Bacho Kiro Cave: transition from late middle Paleolithic through middle/Late Paleolithic. *In: Popov, H. (Ed.), Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2018*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Bulged, Sofia, 4–6 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Sirakov, N., Tsanova, T., Hublin, J.-J., Sirakova, S., McPherron, S., Aldeias, V., Talamo, S., Smith, G., Krumov, I., Spasov, R., Zahariev, N., Fewllas, H., Marreiros, J., Rezek, Z., Martisius, N., Sinet-Mathiot, V. 2018. Bacho Kiro: new data on the middle-Late Palaeolithic transition. *In: Vagalinski, L. (Ed.), Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2017*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Bulged, Sofia, 5–8 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Sirakov, N., Tsanova, T., Hublin, J.-J., Aldeias, V., McPherron, S., Marreiros, J., Krumov, I., Sinet-Mathiot, V., Spassov, R. 2016a. Late Paleolithic sequence in Bacho Kiro Cave: Reopening of investigations. *In: Aladzhov, A. (Ed.), Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2015*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Multiprint, Sofia, 46–50 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Slavchev, V., Kovachev, K., Parvanov, S. 2018a. Archaeological excavations at the Temnata Douпка Cave (Beloslav Cave) nearby the town of Beloslav, Varna District. *In: Vagalinski, L. (Ed.), Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2017*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Bulged, Sofia, 11–13 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Slavchev, V., Parvanov, S., Kovachev, K., Gurova, M., Hristova, L., Karastoyanova N. 2018b. Excavations of the Chalcolithic settlement in the Koriata Locality near the town of Suvorovo, Varna District. *In: Vagalinski, L. (Ed.), Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2017*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Bulged, Sofia, 37–39 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Smíd, J., Aghoví, T., Velenský, D., Moravec, J., Balej, P., Naumov, B., Popgeorgiev, G., Üzüm, N., Avci, A., Jablonski, D. 2021. Quaternary range dynamics and taxonomy of the Mediterranean collared dwarf racer, *Platyceps collaris* (Squamata: Colubridae). *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society* 193, 655–672, <https://doi.org/10.1093/zoolinnean/zlaa151>.
- Sommer, R.S., Benecke, N. 2006. Late Pleistocene and Holocene development of the felid fauna (Felidae) of Europe: a review. *Journal of Zoology* 269 (1), 7–19, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7998.2005.00040.x>.
- Spassov, N. 1997a. Varshets and Slivnitsa – new localities of Villafranchian vertebrate fauna from Bulgaria (taxonomic composition, biostratigraphy and climatochronology). *Geologica Balcanica* 27 (1–2), 83–90, <https://doi.org/10.52321/GeolBalc.27.1-2.83>.
- Spassov, N. 1997b. Villafranchian succession of mammalian megafaunas from Bulgaria and the biozonation of South-East Europe. *In: Aguilar, J.-P., Legendre, S., Michaux, J. (Eds), Actes du Congrès Biochrom'97. Mémoires et travaux de l'Institut de Montpellier de l'Ecole Pratique Hautes Etudes* 21, 669–676.
- Spassov, N. 1982. Evolution and distribution of the European polecat and the Steppe polecats. *Priroda* 6, 32–39 (in Bulgarian).
- Spassov, N. 1982. Fossils of the Ibex and the Irish elk in Bulgaria and the role of the antlers in the Irish elk. *Priroda* 5, 21–7 (in Bulgarian).
- Spassov, N. 1992. Skeletal morphology, ecology and competition of the Aurochs and European bison in the Holocene of Europe. *In: Spitz, F. (Ed.), Proceedings of the Symposium "Ungulates 91"*, Toulouse, 57–61.
- Spassov, N. 2001. Zorillas (Carnivora, Mustelidae, Ictonychini) from the Villafranchian of Bulgaria with a description of a new species of *Baranogale* Kormos, 1934. *Geodiversitas* 23 (1), 87–104.
- Spassov, N. 2003. The Plio-Pleistocene vertebrate fauna in South-Eastern Europe and the megafaunal migratory waves from the east to Europe. *Revue de paléobiologie* 22 (1), 197–229.
- Spassov, N. 2010. The Southwesternmost distribution of the Saiga in the Holocene of Europe: a *Saiga tatarica* find from an archaeological site in Bulgaria. *In: Gatsov, I., Guadelli, J.-L. (Eds), Saxa Loquuntur. Volume in Honour of the 65th Anniversary of Nikolay Sirakov*. Avalon, Sofia, 317–322.
- Spassov, N. 2011. *Acinonyx pardinensis* (Croizet & Jobert) remains from the Middle Villafranchian locality of Varshets (Bulgaria) and the Plio-Pleistocene history of the cheetahs in Eurasia. *Estudios Geológicos* 67 (2), 245–253, <https://doi.org/10.3989/egeol.40464.187>.
- Spassov, N. 2016. On the origin of Wisent, again. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 23, 207–209.
- Spassov, N., Bozkov, D. 1983. Rapport sur le lion de caverne et le lion de l'antiquité aux Balkans et en Bulgarie. *In: Dinev,*

- L. (Chief Ed.), *Proceedings of the European Regional Conference on Speleology*, Sofia, 228–233.
- Spassov, N., Crégut-Bonnoure, E. 1999. First data on the Villafranchian Bovidae of Bulgaria. *Comptes rendus de l'Académie des Sciences* 328 (7), 493–498, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1251-8050\(99\)80151-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1251-8050(99)80151-7).
- Spassov, N., Iliev, N. 1986. Bone remains of wisent (*Bison bonasus* L.) in the medieval settlement near Garvan village, Silistra District (new investigations). In: Vazharova, Z. (Ed.), *The Medieval Settlement Near Garvan Village, Silistra District, 6th–11th c. A.D.* Bulgarian Academy of Sciences Academic Press, Sofia, p. 68.
- Spassov, N., Iliev, N. (in press). Analyses of the bones from domestic and wild mammals from the Bronze Age settlement near Baley. In: Alexandrov, S. (Ed.), *Baley, the Settlement From the Late Bronze Age*, Sofia.
- Spassov, N., Iliev, N. 1994. Animal remains from the submerged late Eneolithic - Early Bronze Age settlements in Sozopol (South Bulgarian Black Sea Coast). *Proceedings of the Internacioanal Symposium Thracia Pontica*, Sofia, 287–314.
- Spassov, N., Iliev, N. 1997. The wild horses of Eastern Europe and the polyphyletic origin of the domestic horse. *Anthropozoologica* 25–26, 753–761.
- Spassov, N., Iliev, N. 2002. The animal bones from the prehistoric necropolis near Durankulak (NE Bulgaria) and the latest record of *Equus hydruntinus* Regalia. In: Todorova, H. (Ed.), *Durankulak. Band II. Teil 1. Die Prähistorischen Gräberfelder von Durankulak*. Deutsches Archäologisches Institut – Berlin. Anubis Publishing House, Sofia, 313–324.
- Spassov, N., Iliev, N. 2007. Promachon – Topolnica. Comparative study of the Domestic and wild Animals from the Sector Topolnica. In: Todorova, H., Stefanovich, M., Ivanov, G. (Eds), *The Struma/Strymon River Valley in Prehistory. Proceedings of the International Symposium Strymon Praehistoricus, Kjustendil–Blagoevgrad (Bulgaria), Serres-Amphipolis (Greece)*, Sofia, 519–522.
- Spassov, N., Iliev, N. 2014. Chapter XII. Faunal remains from Early Neolithic Yabalkovo Chapter XII. 1. Bone remains from domestic and wild animals. In: Roodenberg, J., Leshtakov, K., Petrova, V. (Eds), *Maritsa Project. Volume 2. Yabalkovo. ATE – Ars et Technica Explicatus*. Sofia University “St Kliment Ohridski”, Sofia, 425–432.
- Spassov, N., Popov, V. 2007. History of the formation of the Bulgarian mammalian fauna. In: Popov, Spassov N., Ivanova T., Mihova B., Georgiev K. (Eds), *Mammals Important for Conservation in Bulgaria*. Dutch Mammal Society VZZ, Sofia, 31–47 (in Bulgarian).
- Spassov, N., Raychev, D. 1997. Late Wurm *Panthera pardus* remains from Bulgaria: the European fossil leopards and the question of the probable species survival until the Holocene on the Balkans. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 7, 71–96.
- Spassov, N., Stoychev T. 2003. On the origin of the Wisent, *Bison bonasus* (Linnaeus, 1758). Presence of the Wisent in the Late Palaeolithic rock art of Eurasia. In: Petculescu, A., Stiuică, E. (Eds), *Advances in Paleontology “Hent to Panthera”*, *Papers in Honour of C. Radulescu and P.M. Samson*. Institute of Speleology, Bucharest, 125–130.
- Spassov, N., Hristova, L., Iliev, N. 2018. The domesticated horses from the submerged prehistoric village of Urdoviza (Kiten) on the Bulgarian Black Sea coast – among the oldest known. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 25, 11–14.
- Spassov, N., Hristova, L., Ivanova, S., Georgiev, I. 2017. First record of the “small cave bear” in Bulgaria and the taxonomic status of bears of the *Ursus savini* Andrews – *Ursus rossicus* Borissiak group. *Fossil Imprint* 73 (3–4), 275–291, <https://doi.org/10.2478/if-2017-0015>.
- Spassov, N., Iliev, N., Boev, Z. 2001. Animal remains from the Eneolithic site near the village of Dolnoslav, Plovdiv District, South Bulgaria. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 13, 159–179 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Spassov, N., Karastoyanova, N., Chohadzhiev, S. 2015. The remains of wild and domestic animals from the Late Chalcolithic tell settlement of Hotnitsa (Northern Bulgaria). *Archaeologia Bulgarica* 19 (2), 1–21.
- Stallibrass, S. 2010. Body Parts, Placements, and People in an Iron Age Town in Bulgaria. In: Cmpana, D., Crabtree, P., deFrance, S.D., Lev-Tov, J., Coyke, A. (Eds), *Anthropological Approaches to Zooarchaeology. Complexity, Colonialism, and Animal Transformations*. Oxford Books, Oxford, 56–64.
- Stoianov, I. 1904. La grotte “Toplia” près du la village de Goliama-Jéliazna. *Travaux de la Société bulgare des Sciences naturelles* 2, 103–172 (in Bulgarian, with French abstract).
- Stoychev, R., Nedev, D., Taneva, S., Petkova, K. 2014. Rescue archaeological study of a land property 8642 in the Budzhaka locality near Sozopol, Burgas Region. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1983*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. TDG Print, Sofia, 54–57.
- Szyndlar, Z. 1991a. A review of Neogene and Quaternary snakes of Central and Eastern Europe. Part I: Scolecophidia, Boidae, Colubrinae. *Estudios Geológicos* 47 (1–2), 103–126, <https://doi.org/10.3989/egool.91473-4422>.
- Szyndlar, Z. 1991b. A review of Neogene and Quaternary snakes of Central and Eastern Europe. Part II: Natricinae, Elapidae, Viperidae. *Estudios Geológicos* 47 (3–4), 237–266, <https://doi.org/10.3989/egool.91473-4422>.
- Taneva, S., Ganetsovski, G., Tsanova, T., Dimitrova, I., Chukalev, K., Popov, P., Hodkevich, A., Spasov, R. 2012. Drilling examinations in the Toplitsa Cave, near the Kunino village, Vratsa Region. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2011*. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 38–40 (in Bulgarian).
- Tonkova, M. Vasileva, M. 2011. Archaeological study of the Thracian sanctuary near the Babyak village, Western Rhodopes (Belitsa Municipality, Blagoevgrad District) in 2010: top sector. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2010*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 179–181 (in Bulgarian).
- Tsarov, I. 1994. Rescue excavations of the mound X 2 of necropolis near Golemani village, Veliko Tqarnovo Region. In: Velkov, V., Katincharov, R. (Eds), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1992–1993*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Veliko Tarnovo, 44–45 (in Bulgarian).
- Tsontchev, D. 1942. Le sanctuaire Thrace près du village de Varvara et les antiquites dans ses environs. *Annuaire de la Bibliothèque Nationale et du Musée National de Plovdiv 1940–1941*. Imprimerie de l'État, Sofia, 61–87 (in Bulgarian, with French abstract).
- Vagalinski, L. 2016. Heraclea Sintica. In: Aladzhev, A. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2015*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Multiprint, Sofia, 512–515 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Vagalinski, L. 2017. Heraclea Sintica. In: Vagalinski, L. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2016*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Bulged, Sofia, 301–303 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).

- Vagalinski, L. 2019. Deultum, NW corner turret of the late antique fortress (Site 11). In: Popov, H. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2018*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Bulged, Sofia, 334–336 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Vagalinski, L., Cholakov, I., Aleksandrova, S. 2012. Archaeological excavations of the Object “Antique town Heraclea Sintica with adjacent necropoles” in the Rupite locality, land of the Rupite Village, Municipality of Petrich. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2011*. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 302–305 (in Bulgarian).
- Vagalinski, L., Cholakov, I., Aleksandrova, S., Ivanova, I., Harbaliyeva, D., Sharankov, N. 2012. Antique settlement near Slivarovo village, Malko Tarnovo Region. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2011*. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 368–369 (in Bulgarian).
- Vajsov, I., Zidarov, P., Evlogiev, Y., Karastoyanova, N. 2016. Rescue excavations at Izvor Neolithic settlement (IBS Bulgaria-Serbia, Site 10a). In: Aladzhev, A. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2015*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Multiprint, Sofia, 82–84 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Vasilev, V. 1981. Second finding of wisent (*Bison bonasus* L.) in Bulgaria with a contribution towards the question of the osteological differences between the wisent and the cattle. *Interdisciplinary Studies* 7–8, 89–97 (in Bulgarian).
- Vasilev, V. 1985. Investigation of the fauna from the settlement hill Ovcharovo. *Interdisciplinary Studies* 13, 1–200 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Vasilev, V. 1989. Animal husbandry and hunting in the life of the population from the medieval settlement near Durankulak. In: Todorova H. (Ed.), *Durankulak*. Bulgarian Academy of Sciences Publishing House, Sofia, 223–242 (in Bulgarian).
- Vasilev, V., Dishev, P. 1986. Excavations of the Bozhenishki Urvich fortress. In: Velkov, V. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1985*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Veliko Tarnovo, 172–173 (in Bulgarian).
- Vazharova, Z. 1979. Excavations of the necropolis near the Great Basilica – Pliska. In: Velkov, V., Katincharov, R. (Eds.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1978*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Pazardzhik, 120–121 (in Bulgarian).
- Velichkov, Z. 2010. Rescue archaeological studies of the “Amphitheatreum Serdicaense”. In: Gergova, D. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2009*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 353–355 (in Bulgarian).
- Velkov, V., Getov, L., Rabadzhiev, K., Tancheva-Vasileva, N., Iliev, I., Draganov, D., Ribarov, G., Sasalov, D. 1986. Excavations in Kabile and its vicinities. In: Velkov, V. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1985*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Veliko Tarnovo, 76–80 (in Bulgarian).
- Velkov, V., Milcheva, A., Tancheva, N., Popov, Z. 1973. Excavations in the Thracian town Kabile (Yambol). In: Velkov, V., Naydenova, V. (Eds.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 1972*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum, Nova Zagora, 24–26 (in Bulgarian).
- Venelinova, S., Gurova, M., Karastoyanova, N. 2013. Archaeological excavations of the Chalcolithic settlement mound near the Ivanovo village, Shumen Region. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2012*. National Institute of Archeology and Museum. Kolbis Publishing House, Sofia, 69–71 (in Bulgarian).
- Venelinova, S., Gurova, M., Popova, T., Zidarov, P., Karastoyanova, N. 2012. Archeological excavations of the Chalcolithic settlement mound near the Ivanovo village, Shumen Region in 2010. In: Gurova, M. (Ed.), *Archeological Discoveries and Excavations in 2011*. Avangard Publishing House, Sofia, 72–75 (in Bulgarian).
- Waluszewska-Bubien, A., Krupska, A. 1983. Szcatki kostne ptakow ze Stanowiska Novae (Bulgaria). *Roczniki Akademii Rolniczej w Poznaniu* 145, 145–154.
- Yurinich, S. 1891. Cave Polichki near Dryanovski Monastery St. Archangel Mihail. *Sbornik za narodni umotvoreniya, Nauka s knizhnina* 6, 362–378 (in Bulgarian).